

Ethical Technology Adoption in Public Administration Services

Funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework

Deliverable 2.4

Legal implications of the use of disruptive technologies in the public sector

The Framework Programme for Research & Innovation
Research and Innovation actions (RIA)

ETAPAS

ETHICAL TECHNOLOGY ADOPTION IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION
SERVICES

Grant Agreement Number: 101004594

[H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-2020] Socioeconomic and Cultural
Transformations in the context of the fourth industrial revolution

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D2.4 – Legal implications of the use of disruptive technologies in the public sector

Deliverable No.	D2.4		
Work Package No.	WP2	Work Package Title	Responsible DT adoption: ethical principles and legal framework definition
Task No.	T2.4	Task Title	EU Legal Framework Analysis
Lead beneficiary	UNIGRAZ		
Dissemination level	Public		
Nature of Deliverable	Report		
Delivery date	30th of June 2021		
Status	F: Final		
File Name:	[ETAPAS] D2.4 - Legal implications of the use of disruptive technologies in the public sector.pdf		
Project start date, duration	01 November 2020, 36 Months		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement n°101004594

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Document history			
<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Status</i>	<i>Modifications made by</i>
1	17 May 2021	1 st Draft version of the full deliverable	UNIGRAZ
2	15 June 2021	2 nd Draft version of the full deliverable	UNIGRAZ
3	30 June 2021	3 rd Version of the full deliverable	MEF

List of definitions & abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ADM	Automated decision-making
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CFR	Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
DSII	Directorate of Information Systems and Innovation
DTs	Disruptive technologies
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
ECtHR	European Court of Human Rights
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
EU	European Union
Euratom	Treaty on the European Atomic Energy Community
ETAPAS	Ethical Technology Adoption in Public Administration Services
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPSD	General Product Safety Directive
MEF	Ministry of Economy and Finance
PLD	Product Liability Directive
TEU	Treaty on the European Union
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union

The ETAPAS Consortium consists of:

Logo	Organisation acronym and name	County
	MEF – Ministero dell’Economia e delle Finanze	Italy
	PwC – PricewaterhouseCoopers Public Sector Srl	Italy
	2021.AI – 2021.AI APS	Denmark
	SINTEF – SINTEF AS	Norway
	PROKOM – Sem & Stenersen Prokom AS	Norway
	CERTH – Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis	Greece
	IIT – Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia	Italy
	LC – The Lisbon Council for Economic Competitiveness ASBL	Belgium
	KTH – Kungliga Tekniska Hoegskolan	Sweden
	CEA – Commissariat à l’énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives	France
	FDG – Fondazione Don Carlo Gnocchi Onlus	Italy
	MUKA – Municipality of Katerini	Greece
	UNIGRAZ – University of Graz	Austria
	KI – Karolinska Institutet	Sweden

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1. Executive Summary

Taking the ETAPAS use cases as examples, this deliverable examines the EU legal framework for the implementation of disruptive technologies (DTs) in the public administrative sector. While the use cases raise a range of legal questions, this deliverable focuses on questions regarding EU public law and the state-citizen relationship. It first examines general primary law sources, including the EU's competences to act, market freedoms, key principles, and fundamental rights. It finds several constraints on public administrations' implementation of DTs, as administrations must respect fundamental rights and only act as empowered to do so under primary law. However, there are also opportunities for the administration to implement DTs where it can act in a proportionate and precautionary way within the EU legal framework.

The deliverable then explores key sources of secondary law in relation to the use cases and DTs generally. Focusing on secondary law issues generally applicable to DTs, it examines the General Data Protection Regulation, key product laws, equality directives, and the proposed AI Regulation. It finds that the secondary law framework concretizes the general rules and principles of primary law to create specific obligations on public administrations. However, the application of the existing framework to DTs is not always clear, given new challenges such as discrimination by proxy and automated decision-making. The proposed AI Regulation is a promising blueprint for the future of technology-specific regulation. Following a brief overview of non-binding legal documents issued by EU law- and policymakers, this deliverable concludes that future risk-based regulation is likely to seek to strengthen the framework for the implementation of DTs in the public administrative sector.

1.1 Introduction

Disruptive technologies (DTs)¹ are no longer solely the purview of entrepreneurs or tech giants. Governments around the world are investing in new technologies and asking how they can implement DTs in the public sector. In doing so, public administrations must comply with legal frameworks that are challenged by DTs in novel ways.

The Horizons 2020 Project "Ethical Technology Adoption in Public Administration Services" ("ETAPAS") aims to collaboratively develop a framework for the responsible use of DTs in the public sector with representatives of EU public authorities. The project focuses on four use cases of DTs currently in use or development by public authorities. Taking the use cases as examples (see below), in this deliverable we explore the EU legal framework for the implementation of DTs in the public sector.

This deliverable is not intended as an exhaustive analysis of all possible legal issues arising in relation to the use cases and DTs. For example, the use cases raise questions in several legal areas, both inside and outside the scope of the EU legal framework and in private and public law. Our focus is, however, on legal questions regarding EU public law and the state-citizen relationship. Further, some legal issues such as privacy and data protection arise for many DTs, while some are specific to the nature of the DT in question. We consider generally applicable issues in this deliverable, while specific issues relating to each use case will be examined separately in the use case legal assessments under ETAPAS Work Package 4. Finally, as ETAPAS Deliverable D2.1 contains a separate literature review on the ethical and social implications of DTs,² we do not explore these in this deliverable.

The four ETAPAS use cases are as follows:

- 1 The "Ethically Responsible Big Open Data" use case publishes open data sets concerning public employees. The Directorate of Information Systems and Innovation (DSII), which is a part of Italy's Ministry of Economy and Finance (MEF), provides human resource services to around 100 public administration bodies, dealing with the administration of 2.2 million public servants in Italy. DSII publishes anonymized and aggregated

¹ For the origins of the term, see *Bower/Christensen, Catching the Wave*, Harvard Business Review (1995) <https://hbr.org/1995/01/disruptive-technologies-catching-the-wave> (last downloaded 28th of April 2021); *Christensen, The Innovator's Dilemma; How New Technologies Cause Great Firms to Fail*. Harvard Business School Press (1997).

² See ETAPAS Deliverable 2.1: Literature review on ethical, legal and social aspects of disruptive technologies.

sets of data collected through these services (such as data about individual working relationships, tax deductions, reasons for hiring, etc.) on an open data portal accessible to the public.³ This use case aims to promote the idea of transparency in the public sector and to “maximize the information assets” of the public administration.⁴

As this use case involves the collation of large amounts of sensitive data, it may threaten the fundamental rights to private life and data protection. Although the General Data Protection Regulation (“GDPR”)⁵ is generally not applicable to anonymized data,⁶ it is possible that the data used in this use case could be re-identifiable, and DSII and MEF seek to comply with the GDPR as a matter of best practice. This use case raises several questions under data protection law: who can access the information? How is it stored and used? Are automated decisions made on the basis of the data and which consequences could that could have consequences entail for individuals? What information is provided to data subjects and what safeguards are in place? Further, the principle of equality under EU law may be threatened if this use case draws inferences from big data that could then be used for future modelling or policy decisions that treat different communities unequally.

- 2 The “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” use case is developed by the Italian Institute of Technology in partnership with the Don Gnocchi Foundation, and assesses a patient’s walking abilities in rehabilitation, interacts verbally with the patient, and delivers therapy programs.⁷ The robot collects information about patients’ conditions, recovery and behavior. The “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” aims to enhance patients’ treatment, as well as to increase efficiency and allocate medical resources.

The “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” use case similarly involves the collection of potentially sensitive personal information in the context of health data, and similar questions arise under the fundamental rights to private life and data protection and the GDPR: how and where is data stored? Is it used for other purposes? How does the robot make decisions about the delivery and adaptation of treatment for individual patients? This use case may also impact other fundamental rights, particularly the fundamental rights to human dignity and the right to life. Patients’ autonomy and dignity may be affected by interacting with a non-human interface. The “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” use case, as a form of medical hardware and software, may present dangers to the right to life when it interacts with patients. However, the extent to which fundamental rights concerns are triggered depends on the role of the state in the use case. Does the state only provide financing, or is it directly involved in the development and deployment of the robot?

As this use case involves software integrated into a physical product, it is also likely to engage product safety law such as the General Product Safety Directive (GPSD)⁸ and the Product Liability Directive (PLD)⁹.

- 3 The “Municipality Chatbot Kari” use case is currently in use by 80 Norwegian local municipalities. The AI-based chatbot answers citizens’ questions about municipality services using more than 6,000 prepared answers.¹⁰ Kari serves around 30% of the Norwegian population and is currently being rolled out in Sweden, Finland and Denmark. As Kari’s interactions resemble human conversation, users regularly provide

³ See MEF, NoiPA OpenData <https://dati-noipa.mef.gov.it/cl/en/web/open-data/il-progetto> (last downloaded 28th of April 2021).

⁴ See MEF, NoiPA OpenData <https://dati-noipa.mef.gov.it/cl/en/web/open-data> (last downloaded 15th of June 2021).

⁵ Regulation 2016/679/EU.

⁶ Recital 26 GDPR.

⁷ See ETAPAS, Use case 2: Robot-mediated rehabilitation (IIT-FDG) <https://www.etapasproject.eu/usecases/post-2/> (last downloaded 28th of April 2021); Boost.ai, Automation for the people: using conversational AI to benefit the public sector <https://www.boost.ai/articles/automation-for-the-people-using-conversational-ai-to-benefit-the-public-sector> (last downloaded 28th of April 2021).

⁸ Directive 2001/95/EC.

⁹ Directive 85/374/EEC.

¹⁰ See Prokom, Kommune-Kari <https://prokom.no/kari/> (last downloaded 28th of April 2021).

sensitive information to Kari about mental health and personal issues. The aim of implementing the use case is to assist employees in the municipalities, to increase the efficiency of existing workflows, and to reduce costs.

This use case also creates concerns regarding the fundamental rights to private life and data protection and the GDPR, as it receives and processes personal information and may use that to respond to individuals: What happens to that information? Can it be used for training or other purposes? Similarly, to the “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” use case, this use case may also affect the right to human dignity as citizens interact with a non-human interface. Do they know that Kari is a chatbot? Do they have a choice to interact with a human instead? Do they know if their communications are recorded for learning or other purposes? Further, what role do Norwegian municipalities play in the implementation of the use case? Could the Norwegian state be held accountable for wrong information given by the chatbot? Do they know that they are communicating with a machine and not with a civil servant?

- 4 Finally, the “Public Organizations Multi-factor Misinformation Handling” use case is being implemented by CERTH and the Municipality of Katerini (MUKA) in Greece.

Within this use case, news feeds and social media will be collected and analysed with a focus on location specific information that pertains to the living conditions of immigrants. The raw data retrieved from these sources will be processed and only the content of the article or posts will be used for topic extraction purposes and sense the local’s acceptance regarding immigrants and help in the restriction of criminality and violence within the municipality of crime. All personal information will be anonymised. Alongside, an AI platform that analyses the collected information in order to sense the public opinion, detect misinformation and “fake news”, and identify, classify, and prioritize key topics extracted will be implemented.¹¹ Moreover, the “Public Organizations Multi-factor Misinformation Handling” use case will safe-mark the trusted sources, aiming to provide valid and adequate information for the municipality that can be used for decision-making.

If the state is involved in controlling available content, this use case may infringe the fundamental right to freedom of expression as well as the fundamental right to private life. How is the term “misinformation” defined? Who decides which information to audit and block, and what is the role of the Katerini municipality? How much human oversight is involved in the decision-making process? How is proportionate action ensured? Can people still access the information they wish to access?

In this deliverable, we first define DTs (chapter 2) before exploring the EU legal framework (chapter 3). We analyze the general constraints under primary law on public administrations’ abilities to act within the EU legal framework to regulate DTs (competences, key principles, proportionality, precaution, and equality, market freedoms and fundamental rights) (section 3.1) then consider key sources of secondary law in relation to the use cases and DTs generally (the GDPR, product laws, equality directives, and the proposed AI Regulation) (section 3.2). We then give an overview of the non-binding EU legal framework, namely non-binding documents issued by EU law- and policymakers, that provide insight into future regulation and current concerns (chapter 4). Finally, we offer our perspective (chapter 5) on the existing EU legal framework and how future regulation might seek to strengthen the framework for the implementation of DTs in the public administrative sector.

¹¹ See ETAPAS, Public Organizations Multi-factor Misinformation Handling (CERTH-MUKA) <https://www.etapasproject.eu/usecases/post-4/> (last downloaded 28th of April 2021).

2. Defining Disruptive Technologies

The concept of DTs has its roots in business theory and traditionally defines DTs as technologies that disrupt a market.¹² As disruption often arises from technology being *used* in an innovative way, rather than from the technology itself, DTs are also referred to as “disruptive innovations”.¹³ *Gobble* describes the key features of a disruptive innovator: “disruptive innovators gain a foothold in the market either by creating a low-end product that appeals to customers for whom existing products are too much – too complex, too expensive, too difficult – or by addressing a set of costumers overlooked or ignored by mainstream competitors”.¹⁴

However, this definition of a product that is easier or cheaper than existing offerings, or that addresses a new market, does not adequately capture the range of DTs that ETAPAS explores. In other contexts, such as in government, the term is often understood in a wider sense.¹⁵ Given our particular focus on the public administration introducing these technologies itself, the use cases do not all emerge under market conditions or necessarily aim to supplant existing offerings. However, these technologies will involve structural shifts in the citizen-state relationship. Accordingly, our working definition of DTs (in line with ETAPAS deliverable 2.1) includes:

technologies with the potential to drastically alter the processes and operations in a particular field of the public sector.¹⁶

This definition captures the four use cases set out above, as well as a range of other technologies. The “Ethically Responsible Big Open Data” use case will disrupt the structure of the public administration to become a transparent source of open data that can be used for further research. The “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” use case disrupts the relationship between doctor and patient, using a robot to deliver rehabilitation services. The “The municipal chatbot Kari” use case similarly disrupts the state-citizen relationship as citizens receive information from an AI-enabled chatbot rather than a human being. Finally, the “Public Organizations Multi-factor Misinformation Handling” use case disrupts the state-citizen relationship as the state engages in new forms of information monitoring and collecting information for new purposes.

3. Binding EU Legal Framework

The EU legal framework is made up of primary law and secondary law. In this chapter, we analyze primary law and secondary law in turn to reflect the hierarchy of EU law. Every action taken by the EU requires a basis in primary law, primarily made up of key treaties that provide the functional rules for the EU’s powers to act. Secondary law implements the objectives of primary law, mostly through directives and regulations. While directives must usually be transformed into national law by the member states (indirect effect), regulations are directly applicable (direct effect).¹⁷

¹² See *Christensen*, Dilemma.

¹³ See *Gobble*, Defining Disruptive Innovation, Research Technology Management 2016, 66.

¹⁴ *Gobble*, Research Technology Management 2016, 66.

¹⁵ See *Ronzhyn/Wimmer/Spitzer/Pereira/Alexopoulos*, Using disruptive technologies in government: Identification of research and training needs, International Conference on Electronic Government 2019, 276; *Gobble*, Research Technology Management 2016, 66.

¹⁶ *Ronzhyn/Wimmer/Spitzer/Pereira/Alexopoulos*, Using disruptive technologies in government: Identification of research and training needs, International Conference on Electronic Government 2019, 276-287.

¹⁷ Art 288 TFEU.

Figure 1 – Binding EU Legal Framework

3.1 Primary Law

Primary law

The main written primary sources of EU law are the founding treaties: The Treaty on the EU ("TEU"), the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU ("TFEU"), and the Treaty on the European Atomic Energy Community (Euratom). The TEU and the TFEU set out the competences, principles and market freedoms of the EU.¹⁸

- The competences set out in the treaties determine whether and to what extent the EU is competent to regulate DTs.
- Key principles also affect the implementation of DTs, such as the proportionality principle,¹⁹ the precautionary principle,²⁰ and the principle of equality and non-discrimination.²¹

¹⁸See *Schütze, European Union Law*² (2018) 81.

¹⁹ Art 5(4) TFEU.

²⁰ Art 191 TFEU.

²¹ Art 18 TFEU.

- The market freedoms are closely linked to the principle of equality and ensure the functioning of the internal market. The free movement of goods and the freedom to provide services are particularly relevant for the implementation of DTs.

Fundamental rights are protected in the EU legal framework by two key sources: the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (“CFR”)²² and the European Convention on Human Rights (“ECHR”).

We explore the applicable competences and principles set out in the treaties in Chapters 3.1.1 and 3.1.2, followed by the market freedoms in Chapter 3.1.3 and applicable rights in Chapter 3.1.4.

3.1.1 Competences

The EU legal framework for DTs is constrained by the ability of the EU to regulate DTs within the distribution of powers between the EU itself and its member states. In this section, we examine relevant competences under which the EU could act to regulate DTs.

- To answer the question of *when* the EU is competent to regulate DTs, the conferral principle in Art 5(2) TEU states that the EU can only act within the competences it has been granted through the Treaties.²³
- To answer the question of to what *extent* the EU is competent to regulate DTs, the subsidiarity principle obliges the EU to refrain from acting unless its action is more effective than the one taken by all member states.²⁴ Accordingly, the EU can only act to regulate DTs when actions on the member state level are less effective than EU action.

Even where the EU might be theoretically competent to act, the extent it is actually able to act will depend on the applicable type of competence. In principle, there are three different types of competences in the EU.

The first type is *exclusive* competences, which are listed in Art 3 TFEU and include competences in the area of the custom union, monetary policy and a common commercial policy.²⁵ In these cases, only the EU can adopt legislative acts. However, the EU could also empower the member states to adopt legally binding acts.²⁶ The subsidiarity principle does not apply to exclusive competences.²⁷ Secondly, the EU has *shared* competences, under which both the EU and its member states can adopt legally binding acts.²⁸ The subsidiarity principle is applicable here and the EU can only act where its action is more effective than member state action.²⁹ Thirdly, the EU has *supporting* competences. In this area of competences, the EU is able to support, coordinate or complement the actions of its members states.³⁰

²² Chalmers/Davies/Monti, *European Union Law*⁴ (2019) 252.

²³ See Tillotson/Foster, *Text, Cases and Material on European Union Law*⁴ (2003) 56; Neframi, “Within the Scope of European Union Law,” *Beyond the Principle of Conferral?*, in Van der Walt/Ellsworth (eds), *Constitutional Sovereignty and Social Solidarity in Europe* (2015) 69.

²⁴ See Tillotson/Foster, *Text*⁴ 54.

²⁵ Art 3 TFEU.

²⁶ See Schütze, *Law*² 241.

²⁷ See Tillotson/Foster, *Text*⁴ 54.

²⁸ See Schütze, *Law*² 242.

²⁹ See Tillotson/Foster, *Text*⁴ 54 f.

³⁰ See Schütze, *Law*² 245 f.

3.1.1.1 Internal Market (Art 4(2)(a) TFEU, Art 26f TFEU)

The competence to regulate the internal market is a shared competence between the EU and the member states.³¹ The EU has authority to standardize legislation in order to establish and ensure the functioning of the internal market (Art 114 TFEU),³² defined as “an area without internal frontiers in which the free movement of goods, persons, services and capital is ensured in accordance with the provisions of the Treaties”.³³ This definition focuses on market freedoms,³⁴ aiming to remove any barriers to mobility and ensure undistorted competition.³⁵ Therefore, the EU can only adopt measures on the basis of Article 114 TFEU if the national rules about DTs in the public administrative sector could obstruct market freedoms or cause distortions of competition.

In the context of civil law, the European Parliament has already suggested Art 114 TFEU as a legal basis for EU action on robotics and artificial intelligence.³⁶

“The action by the Commission in order to adapt the existing legislation to the reality of robots and artificial intelligence should be based on Article 114 TFEU. [...] The development of robotics is currently happening in the entire Union. In reaction to this innovation, member states are developing different national legislations. These discrepancies are expected to create obstacles for an effective development of robotics. Due to the fact that this technology has cross-border implications, the best legislative option is a European one.”³⁷

Following this view, the proposed AI Regulation is based on Art 114 TFEU.³⁸

The CJEU has also found that the recourse to Art 114 TFEU is justified in the rapidly changing and complex field of technology, where it is foreseeable that legislative differences among the member states are likely to eventuate.³⁹

These legal discrepancies also occur regarding DTs. Each member state has its own national fundamental rights regime and discretion when it comes to the implementation of directives, such as the Data Protection Law Enforcement Directive,⁴⁰ general product safety laws,⁴¹ the Machinery Directive⁴² and the Medical Directive on Medicinal Products,⁴³ for instance. Accordingly, different national rules bind the public administrations of the Member States when implementing DTs. If these discrepancies obstruct market freedoms or cause distortions of competition, the EU would have the authority to standardize legislation on the basis of Art 114 TFEU.

³¹ See *Jäger*, Art 4 AEUV in *Jäger/Stöger* (eds), *Kommentar zu EUV und AEUV* (2020) para 13; *Calliess* Art 4 AEUV in *Calliess/Ruffert* (eds) *EUV / AEUV: das Verfassungsrecht der Europäischen Union mit Europäischer Grundrechtecharta*⁵ (2016) para 5.

³² See *Piska*, in *Jäger/Stöger* (eds) Art 26 AEUV para 7.

³³ Art 26(2) TFEU.

³⁴ See *Jäger*, in *Jäger/Stöger* (eds) Art 4 AEUV para 14.

³⁵ See *Piska*, in *Jäger/Stöger* (eds) Art 26 AEUV para 7.

³⁶ See European Parliamentary Research Service, *European framework on ethical aspects of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies* (2020) 17.

³⁷ See European Parliament, *Draft Report with recommendations to the Commission on Civil Law Rules on Robotics*, 2015/2103 INL (2016) 21.

³⁸ See European Commission, *Proposal for a Regulation on a European approach for Artificial Intelligence*, COM (2021) 206 final, 6.

³⁹ See Case C-217/04, *United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland vs European Parliament and Council of the European Union* para 62.

⁴⁰ Directive 2016/680/EU.

⁴¹ See Chapter 3.2.2.

⁴² Directive 2006/42/EG.

⁴³ Directive 2001/83.

3.1.1.2 Consumer Protection (Art 4(2)(f) TFEU, Art 169 TFEU)

The competence to regulate consumer protection law is focused on the protection of “consumers”. The TFEU does not contain a definition for the term “consumer”,⁴⁴ but the predominant view is that a consumer is a “natural person who does not act for commercial or professional purposes”.⁴⁵ Accordingly, citizens who consume DT services or products would be considered consumers, regardless of whether those DTs are provided by the public administration or private companies.

Consumer protection overlaps considerably with internal market policy,⁴⁶ and Art 114 TFEU is a possible basis for measures to ensure consumer protection.⁴⁷ Art 169(2)(b) also enables the EU to take “measures which support, supplement and monitor the policy pursued by the Member states”.⁴⁸ The EU could therefore use these competences to ensure a high level of consumer protection in relation to DTs.

3.1.1.3 Research and Technological Development (Art 4 para 3 TFEU, Art 179-190 TFEU)

The nature of the competence regarding research and technological development has been subject to debate.⁴⁹ However, Art 4(1) states that competences are shared competences if they are not enlisted in Art 3 or 6 TFEU. Assuming this competence is a shared competence,⁵⁰ and therefore subject to the subsidiarity principle, the EU could draw up and implement programs, such as action and assistance programs, for the implementation of DTs in the public administrative sector.⁵¹ The exercise of those competences would need to “complement” member states’ own activities⁵² and would need to avoid preventing them from exercising their own competences.

3.1.1.4 Common Safety Concerns in Public Health Matters (Art 4(2)(k) TFEU, Art 168 TFEU)

The competence to regulate common safety concerns in public health matters is a shared competence and allows the EU to take certain measures in order to deal with supranational public health safety concerns.⁵³ Common safety concerns in public health matters cover “measures setting high standards of quality and safety for medicinal products and devices for medical use”.⁵⁴ The predominant view assumes that the terms “medicinal product” and “medical device” are to be understood in accordance with the definitions in the Medical Directive On Medicinal Products For Human Use and the Medical Devices Regulation.⁵⁵

According to the Medical Devices Regulation, medical devices are: “any instrument, apparatus, appliance, software, implant, reagent, material or other article intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, for human beings for one or more of the following specific medical purposes”.⁵⁶ The treatment of diseases or injuries is listed as a specific medical purpose.

⁴⁴ See *Zöchling-Jud*, in Jäger/Stöger (eds) Art 169 AEUV para 2.

⁴⁵ See *Zöchling-Jud*, in Jäger/Stöger (eds) Art 169 AEUV para 2; *Lurger/Augenhofer*, Österreichisches und Europäisches Konsumentenschutzrecht² (2008) 34; *Gruber*, Art 169 AEUV in Lenz/Borchardt (eds) EU-Verträge Kommentar: EUV, AEUV, GRCh⁶ (2013) para 6.

⁴⁶ See *Jäger*, Art 4 AEUV in Jäger/Stöger (eds) para 37.

⁴⁷ Art 169(2)(a) TFEU.

⁴⁸ Art 169(2)(b) TFEU.

⁴⁹ Some argue that it is a supporting competence *Nettesheim*, Art 4 AEUV in Grabitz/Hilf/Nettesheim (eds) Das Recht der Europäischen Union⁴⁷ (2012) para 26) others argue that it is a competence of its own – “*aliud*-competence” see *Häde*, Art 4 AEUV in Pechstein/Nowak/Häde (eds) Frankfurter Kommentar zu EUV, GRC und AEUV (2017) para 13.

⁵⁰ Art 4(1) states that competences are shared competences if they are not enlisted in Art 3 or 6 TFEU.

⁵¹ See *Jäger*, Art 4 AEUV in Jäger/Stöger (eds) para 63.

⁵² Art 180 TFEU.

⁵³ See *Jäger*, Art 4 AEUV in Jäger/Stöger (eds) para 56.

⁵⁴ Art 168(4)(c) TFEU.

⁵⁵ Regulations 2001/83/EC and 2017/745/EU. See *Fischer*, Art 168 AEUV in Lenz/Borchardt (eds) para 18; *Kingreen*, in Calliess/Ruffert⁴ (eds) Art 168 AEUV para 22.

⁵⁶ Art 2(1).

Therefore, DTs with medical purposes would be covered by this competence if they raise safety concerns. For example, the “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” use case is likely to be a medical device as it has a medical purpose to treat diseases or injuries. Moreover, the use of robot-mediated rehabilitation raises safety concerns since the robot delivers and adapts treatments for human patients.⁵⁷ Consequently, the EU could take measures to ensure higher quality and safety standards according to Art 168(4)(c) TFEU. Other measures relating to medical devices could also be based on Art 114 TFEU.⁵⁸

3.1.1.5 Health (Art 6(a)TFEU, Art 168 TFEU)

Alongside the legislative powers in the area of health covered by Art 4(2)(k) TFEU, the EU also has (weaker) supporting competences regarding a European Health Policy.⁵⁹ This Policy aims to provide complementary measures which improve public health, prevent human illnesses and diseases and remove sources of danger to physical and mental health.⁶⁰

Art 168(2) TFEU allows the EU to encourage cooperation between member states, to coordinate the programs and health policies of the member states and to support the mutual exchange of information. This supporting competence would enable the EU to initiate a common European Health Policy in regards to the implementation of DTs.

3.1.1.6 Data Protection (Art 16 TFEU)

Art 16 TFEU allows for the adoption of rules relating to the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data both by Union bodies and member states “when carrying out activities which fall within the scope of Union law and the rules relating to the free movement of such data”.⁶¹ Accordingly, this is a shared competence as both the EU and member states may act. Art 16 TFEU served as the basis for the GDPR and has been proposed as a partial basis for the draft AI regulation proposal.⁶² As many DTs raise concerns for data protection, the EU could adopt further rules to address these concerns.

3.1.2 Important Principles

In this section, we discuss the proportionality, precautionary and equality principles. The principle of proportionality is a key principle of EU law,⁶³ and provides an operative constraint on EU actions as all EU actions must be proportionate to EU objectives and not go beyond what is necessary.⁶⁴ This principle is accordingly an important consideration in the context of the public administration seeking to introduce DTs.

The precautionary principle stems from environmental law,⁶⁵ and has become enshrined as a general principle of EU law that ensures “a high level of protection of health, consumer safety and the

⁵⁷ See ETAPAS, Use case 2: Robot-mediated rehabilitation (IIT-FDG) <https://www.etapasproject.eu/usecases/post-2/> (last downloaded on the 5th of March 2021).

⁵⁸ See *Schmidt am Busch*, Art 168 AEUV in Grabitz/Hilf/Nettesheim⁴⁷ (eds) para 57.

⁵⁹ See *Jäger*, Art 4 AEUV in *Jäger/Stöger* (eds) para 16.

⁶⁰ See *Schneider*, Art 4 AEUV in *Jäger/Stöger* (eds) para 16.

⁶¹ Art 19 TFEU.

⁶² See Chapter 3.3.4.

⁶³ Article 5(4) TEU.

⁶⁴ See C-58/08 *Vodafone and Others*, para 51.

⁶⁵ See Art 191 TFEU (previously Art 174(1) EC): “Union policy on the environment shall aim at a high level of protection taking into account the diversity of situations in the various regions of the Union. It shall be based on the precautionary principle and on the principles that preventive action should be taken, that environmental damage should as a priority be rectified at source and that the polluter should pay.”

environment in all the Community's spheres of activity".⁶⁶ It allows EU decision-makers to act in a precautionary way where they lack sufficient scientific information about a potentially dangerous risk.⁶⁷ As DTs can involve risks to health and the environment, the precautionary principle may not only constrain decision-makers' actions but also empower them to act where they are concerned about DTs but have insufficient data to confirm the level of risk.

The principle of equal treatment and non-discrimination is a key part of the EU legal framework and is found in several EU legal instruments, primarily the TFEU, the CFR, and the ECHR. We provide a general overview of the principle in this section and analyze its more specific implementation through directives in Chapter 3.3.3.

3.1.2.1 Proportionality Principle

The test for proportionality asks whether an action corresponds to objectives of general interest pursued by the EU or whether it is a disproportionate interference that impairs the very substance of a right.⁶⁸ This question is answered in three stages:⁶⁹ Firstly, is the action suitable to achieve the Union's objectives? Secondly, is the action necessary and the least restrictive means to achieve those objectives? Thirdly, does the action avoid imposing a burden that is excessive in relation to the objective? If the answer to all three questions is "yes", the action will be considered proportionate.

However, the CJEU has indicated that it is more reluctant to find the EU's actions disproportionate in matters of high policy that affect collective interests (such as economic decisions) in contrast to actions affecting particular individuals' rights. Where the EU undertakes complex assessments involving political, social and economic choices, the CJEU will only find measures disproportionate if they are "manifestly inappropriate" for the objective.⁷⁰ The CJEU has also shown this deference in relation to "evolving and complex technology", finding that "the European Union legislature has a broad discretion, in particular as to the assessment of highly complex scientific and technical facts in order to determine the nature and scope of the measures which it adopts".⁷¹

Accordingly, the question of proportionality is highly context-dependent and the CJEU is likely to be more reluctant to intervene in high policy decisions involving DTs. However, the principle is a touchstone for all EU action, and actors should regularly assess their own compliance with the requirements of proportionality throughout any implementation process.

3.1.2.2 Precautionary Principle

This principle reflects the unavoidable difficulty in risk assessments that risks cannot always be conclusively identified and measured. Usually, when undertaking a risk assessment, decision-makers must consider available scientific data and cannot base their decisions on purely hypothetical risks.⁷² However, this approach creates issues if the decision-maker fails to act or enacts inadequate measures due to insufficient data, and irreversible harm occurs that cannot be mitigated when the risk is later quantified. The precautionary principle aims to fill this gap by providing that where a lack of data means that it is impossible to determine the extent of a risk, but there is a

⁶⁶ See T-74/00, T-76/00, T-83/00–T-85/00, T-132/00, T-137/00 and T-141/00 *Artegoda GmbH and Others vs Commission*, para 183f; T-429/13 and T-451/13 *Bayer CropScience and Others vs Commission* 2018/C 231/21, para 109.

⁶⁷ See European Commission, Communication on Precautionary Principle, COM (2000) 1 final.

⁶⁸ See C-44/79 *Hauer vs Land Rheinland-Pfalz*, para 23; Case C-293/97 *R vs Secretary of State for the Environment and Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food, ex parte Standley*, para 54.

⁶⁹ See *Craig/de Búrca*, EU law: text, cases, and materials⁶ (2015), 551.

⁷⁰ See C-491/01 *The Queen vs Secretary of State for Health, ex parte British American Tobacco (Investments) Ltd and Imperial Tobacco Ltd*, para 123.

⁷¹ See C-343/09, *Afton Chemical Ltd vs Secretary of State for Transport*, para 28.

⁷² See C-282/15, *Queisser Pharma GmbH & Co. KG vs Bundesrepublik Deutschland*.

likelihood of real harm if the risk should materialize, restrictive measures can be adopted without that data. For example, if it is impossible to determine if waste is hazardous or not, the precautionary principle requires that it be treated as hazardous.⁷³

The principle lacks a formal legal definition at EU law, and confusion over its application (and a request by the Council of the EU for clear guidelines⁷⁴) led the Commission to publish a communication in 2000, outlining its approach to the precautionary principle and guidelines for its application.⁷⁵ The Commission stated that measures based on the proportionality principle must be:⁷⁶

- a) *proportional* to the chosen level of protection: for example, if a risk cannot be determined with certainty but catastrophic harm *may* result, a total ban on actions giving rise to that risk may be considered the only proportionate measure to respond to that risk. Simultaneously, a measure based on the precautionary principle cannot, for example, always aim for *zero* risk, as this is likely to be “disproportionate to the desired level of protection” and is “rarely to be found”;⁷⁷
- b) *non-discriminatory*: measures should treat comparable situations in a similar way;
- c) *consistent* with similar measures: measures should be of comparable scope to measures in similar areas that do have sufficient data available;
- d) based on a *cost/benefit analysis*, which should not be limited to economic considerations, but should also consider non-economic factors such as public palatability and efficiency;
- e) *subject to review* in the light of new data: measures should be amended as and when new data becomes available; and
- f) *capable of assigning responsibility* for producing the scientific evidence necessary for a more comprehensive risk assessment: for example, measures that impose a prior approval process on market access for dangerous goods create a responsibility on businesses to produce scientific evidence that their goods are safe.

Given that the public sector is investing in and trialing DTs in the health sector that may create risks for human health, such as the “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” use case, the precautionary principle is highly relevant. More generally, as DTs often involve considerable use of resources and energy⁷⁸ (e.g.: blockchain technology,⁷⁹ crypto-mining⁸⁰) and may not be easily disposed of or recycled, the potential risk to the environment from DTs should also act as a check on public administrations considering their introduction.

The principle has traditionally granted a power to actors to behave in a precautionary way but may also create a duty to do so.⁸¹ The CJEU has held not only that “where there is uncertainty as to the existence or extent of risks to human health, the institutions may take protective measures without having to wait until the reality and

⁷³ See C-487/17, *Verlezza ua*; T-13/99, *Pfizer Animal Health SA vs Council*.

⁷⁴ See Council, Resolution of 28 June 1999 on Community consumer policy 1999 to 2001, Art II(3).

⁷⁵ See European Commission, COM(2000) 1. Brussels 2.2.2000.

⁷⁶ At 3 – 4.

⁷⁷ European Commission, COM(2000) 1. Brussels 2.2.2000, 17.

⁷⁸ [Coeckelbergh, AI for climate: freedom, justice, and other ethical and political challenges, AI and Ethics 2021, 67.

⁷⁹ See Sedlmeier/Buhl/Fridgen/Keller, The Energy Consumption of Blockchain Technology: Beyond Myth, Business & Information Systems Engineering Volume 62, 2020, 599 ff.

⁸⁰ See J.Li/N.Li/Peng/Cui/Wu, Energy consumption of cryptocurrency mining: A study of electricity consumption in mining cryptocurrencies, Energy Volume 168, 2019, 160 ff.

⁸¹ For an analysis of the *duty* to take the principle into consideration (rather than just a power to do so), see Leonelli, Judicial review of compliance with the precautionary principle from Paraquat to Blaise: Quantitative thresholds, risk assessment and the gap between regulation and regulatory implementation, German Law Journal (2021) 22, 184–215

seriousness of those risks become fully apparent”⁸², but that the precautionary principle may *oblige* a public authority to act “even before any adverse effects have become apparent”.⁸³ Accordingly, where the risks of a DT are not yet certain due to insufficient scientific research or data, the public administration may be obliged to either a) avoid implementing the technology at all, or to b) regulate its introduction through, for example, approval processes that enable it to gather this data.

3.1.2.3 Equality

The principle of equality is firmly enshrined in the EU legal framework. Art 8 and 10 TFEU provide obligations on the Union to “aim to eliminate inequalities, and to promote equality, between men and women”⁸⁴ and to “aim to combat discrimination based on sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation”.⁸⁵ Art 18 TFEU seeks to create a functional internal market⁸⁶ by prohibiting “any discrimination on the grounds of nationality [...] within the scope of application of the Treaties, and without prejudice to any special provisions contained therein”.⁸⁷ It also authorizes the European Parliament and the Council to adopt rules designed to prohibit such discrimination,⁸⁸ and Art 19 authorizes the Council to take “appropriate action to combat discrimination based on sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation”.⁸⁹ Art 18 forms the basis for other fundamental freedoms such as the free movement of goods or the free movement of services. According to the case law of the CJEU, Art 18 TFEU directly applies to member states and prevails over conflicting domestic law.⁹⁰

The CFR also contains a general principle of equality that “everyone is equal before the law”.⁹¹ This general principle is supplemented by specific prohibitions of discrimination and principles of equal treatment.⁹² Art 21 CFR prohibits an open-ended list of “any discrimination based on any ground such as sex, race, color, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation”.⁹³

Art 1 ECHR provides that “the High Contracting Parties shall secure to everyone within their jurisdiction the rights and freedoms defined in Section I of this Convention”.⁹⁴ Art 14 ECHR contains a prohibition of discrimination and “cites a number of reasons why unequal treatment is prohibited”.⁹⁵ It provides a closed list of grounds for discrimination: “the enjoyment of the rights and freedoms set forth in this Convention shall be secured without discrimination on any ground such as sex, race, color, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, association with a national minority, property, birth or other status.”⁹⁶ Art 14 is not violated with every unequal treatment: “an impermissible disadvantage only exists if the disputed differentiation is objectively not

⁸² See C-157/96 *The Queen vs Ministry of Agriculture*, para 63f and C-180/96 *United Kingdom vs Commission*, para 99f.

⁸³ See T-13/99 *Pfizer vs Council of the European Union*, para 444 and T-70/99 *Alpharma Inc. vs Council of the European Union*, para 355, where institutions withdrew their authorizations of foodstuffs additives before any adverse effects had resulted. This approach was held by the CJEU to be consistent with the precautionary principle, “by reason of which a public authority can be required to act even before any adverse effects have become apparent”.

⁸⁴ Art 8 TFEU.

⁸⁵ Art 10 TFEU.

⁸⁶ See *Kucsko-Stadlmayer*, Art 18 AEUV in Jäger/Stöger (eds), EUV/AEUV.

⁸⁷ Art 18 TFEU.

⁸⁸ Art 18 TFEU.

⁸⁹ TFEU, Art 19.

⁹⁰ See *Kucsko-Stadlmayer*, in Jäger/Stöger (eds), EUV/AEUV Art 18 AEUV.

⁹¹ Art 20 CFR.

⁹² See *Berka/Binder/Kneihls*, *Die Grundrechte* (2019) 573-574.

⁹³ Art 21 CFR

⁹⁴ Art 1 ECHR.

⁹⁵ *Grabenwarter/Frank*, B-VG (2020) Art 14 EMRK.

⁹⁶ Art 14 ECHR.

justified, i.e. if it does not pursue a legitimate goal or if the means used are not proportionate to the intended purpose.”⁹⁷

Protocol 12 to the ECHR, which was added in 2000, also refers to “the fundamental principle according to which all persons are equal before the law and are entitled to the equal protection of the law” and that “the principle of non-discrimination does not prevent States Parties from taking measures in order to promote full and effective equality, provided that there is an objective and reasonable justification for those measures”.⁹⁸ Art 1 to this Protocol (which is regarded as part of the ECHR⁹⁹) covers the same grounds of non-discrimination as Art 14 ECHR, but has a wider prohibition on discrimination, as it extends to the enjoyment of any right set forth by law, not just the rights set out in the ECHR.¹⁰⁰ It provides that “no one shall be discriminated against by any public authority on any ground such as those mentioned in paragraph 1”,¹⁰¹ indicating that the prohibition is wider than the listed grounds, so could include, for example, sexual orientation or gender identity.

It is possible that DTs could be used to address inequalities and uphold the principle of equality if they *avoid* human bias¹⁰² rather than reinforcing it, but this potential has not clearly been established to date.¹⁰³ In contrast, the potential of DTs to create inequalities and magnify biases has already been seen in many contexts.¹⁰⁴ An example of biased algorithmic profiling is the use of an algorithm to classify job-seekers by the job support service in Austria, which assigns negative values to factors such as “female” in the calculation of job-seekers’ employability.¹⁰⁵ A person’s “score” then indicates how much support they could be entitled to receive from the job-seeker support program.¹⁰⁶

The use of DTs by public administrations evidently risks breaching the principle of equality and associated directives. This risk is particularly potent in the context of DTs that rely on big data analysis and reflect biases contained in their datasets.¹⁰⁷ For example, if the “Ethically Responsible Big Open Data” use case results in inferences being drawn from big data, the public administration must ensure that it does not use this data to result in differential treatment of social groups.

⁹⁷ See *Grabenwarter/Frank*, B-VG Art 14 EMRK.

⁹⁸ Protocol 12 to the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms Rome, 4.XI.2000.

⁹⁹ Protocol 12, Art 3.

¹⁰⁰ Protocol 12, Art 1.

¹⁰¹ Protocol 12, Art 1.

¹⁰² *Ehrke-Rabel*, Big Data in Tax Collection and Enforcement in Halehner/Kofler/Pantazatou/Rust (eds) *Tax and the Digital Economy: Challenges and Proposals for Reform* (2019) 311 f.

¹⁰³ *Pollicino*, EU Agency for Fundamental Rights “Getting the Future Right – Artificial Intelligence and Fundamental Rights”. A view from the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, *BioLaw Journal – Rivista di BioDiritto*, 1/2021.

¹⁰⁴ See for example, *Allhutter/Cech/Fischer/Grill/Mager*, Algorithmic Profiling of Job Seekers in Austria: How Austerity Politics Are Made Effective, *Front. Big Data* 2020, 3:5; *Ehrke-Rabel*, *Data* 311 f.

¹⁰⁵ *Allhutter/Cech/Fischer/Grill/Mager*, *Front. Big Data* 2020, 3:5.

¹⁰⁶ At 2.

¹⁰⁷ European Parliament, Resolution on fundamental rights implications of big data: privacy, data protection, non-discrimination, security and law-enforcement (2016/2225(INI)).

3.1.3 Market Freedoms

The main objective of the Roman Treaties in 1958 was to establish a common market.¹⁰⁸ Since the common market has been achieved, the EU has invested continuous efforts to ensure and maintain the single EU market.¹⁰⁹ Emerging technologies, such as AI, Big Data and Robotics have enormous growth potential for the EU.¹¹⁰

EU Law has two regulatory approaches to maintain a functioning internal market: *positive* integration aims to implement uniform standards for all member states by issuing directives and regulations, while *negative* integration aims to remove market barriers by implementing certain market freedoms.¹¹¹ There are five market freedoms in total: the free movement of goods (Art 26, 28ff TFEU), the free movement of workers (Art 45 TFEU), the right of establishment (Art 49 TFEU), the freedom to provide services (Art 56 TFEU) and the free movement of capital (Art 63 TFEU).

The market freedoms of free movement of goods and the freedom to provide services are particularly relevant for the implementation of DTs. The digital nature of many DTs means that they can transcend borders in new ways. In this section, we examine how these market freedoms could impact on the implementation of DTs in the EU legal framework.

3.1.3.1 Free Movement of Goods (Art 26, 28ff TFEU)

The free movement of goods allows goods to move within the internal market without any market barriers, such as custom duties or measures of equivalent effect.¹¹² However, the TFEU does not define the term “goods”, which could make it difficult to determine whether a DT is a good or a service. While software systems, which are saved on a data medium (such as a floppy-disk or a USB-stick) are considered goods,¹¹³ software licenses fall under the category of services.¹¹⁴ While machines are products, their technical surveillance and maintenance is a service.¹¹⁵

Moreover, the TFEU does not define the term “measures of equivalent effect”.¹¹⁶ The CJEU has stated that “all trading rules enacted by member states which are capable of hindering, directly or indirectly, actually or potentially, intra-community trade are to be considered as measures having an effect equivalent to quantitative restrictions.”¹¹⁷ However, not every measure that poses a market barrier is automatically a violation of the free movement of goods. Art 36 TFEU contains several grounds for justification, such as the protection of health and life of humans, animals or plants, public security. If there is a ground for justification and the measure is proportionate,¹¹⁸ the free movement of goods is not violated.

¹⁰⁸ See Klamert, EU-Recht² (2018) para 403ff.

¹⁰⁹ See Klamert, EU-Recht² para 403.

¹¹⁰ See European Commission, Advanced technologies https://ec.europa.eu/growth/industry/policy/advanced-technologies_en (downloaded on the 8th of June 2021).

¹¹¹ See Klamert, EU-Recht² para 404.

¹¹² See Klamert, EU-Recht² para 447 ff.

¹¹³ See CJEU C-79/89, No 1991,1-1853(1890,Rn.21) -BrownBoveri.

¹¹⁴ See Frenz, Handbuch Europarecht, Band 1 Europäische Grundfreiheiten (2004) para 679; Müller-Graff, Art 28 in von der Groeben/Schwarze (eds), Europäisches Unionsrecht⁷ (2015) para 275.

¹¹⁵ See CJEU C-55/93, No.1994,1-4837 (4857,Rn.14) -van Schaik.

¹¹⁶ See Klamert, EU-Recht² para 452.

¹¹⁷ See ECJ, 11. 7. 1974, 8-74, *Dassonville*.

¹¹⁸ Regarding the proportionality principle see Chapter 3.1.2.1.

3.1.3.2 Freedom to Provide Services (Art 56 & 57 TFEU)

The freedom to provide services allows EU citizens and legal persons established in the EU to provide or make use of services, including public services,¹¹⁹ in another member state.¹²⁰ Unlike “goods”, “services” are defined in Art 57 TFEU: “Services shall be considered to be “services” within the meaning of the Treaties where they are normally provided for remuneration, in so far as they are not governed by the provisions relating to freedom of movement for goods, capital and persons.”¹²¹ Examples include activities of an industrial and commercial character.¹²² Accordingly, the freedom to provide services also covers DT services provided by the public administration, as long as they have an industrial or commercial character.

According to the CJEU, the freedom to provide services contains the principle of non-discrimination as well as a general prohibition on restrictions.¹²³ While the principle of non-discrimination prohibits direct and indirect discrimination,¹²⁴ the general prohibition on restrictions also covers non-discriminatory measures, which pose a barrier for the internal market or make it impossible.¹²⁵ However, interferences with the freedom to provide services may be justified, if there are grounds for interference and the measure is proportionate.¹²⁶

3.1.4 Fundamental Rights

In this section, we explore the fundamental rights to human dignity, life, private life, data protection, and freedom of expression, as the use cases raise particular issues in relation to these rights. Fundamental rights have traditionally been expressed as rights to be free from state interference in certain areas of life, but they also include obligations on the state to protect and uphold certain protections.¹²⁷

Fundamental rights in the EU legal framework may impact on the introduction of DTs in two ways, either:

- a) creating obligations to *limit* or *avoid* DTs, as residents may have rights to be free from their effects, or
- b) creating obligations to *introduce* DTs, as residents may have rights to the benefits associated with these technologies.

Some rights are absolute and cannot be subject to limitations. For example, the rights to life and freedom from torture are absolute rights that cannot be qualified.¹²⁸ However, most rights are not absolute and can be subject to justified limitations, which can be broadly phrased for some rights. For example, the right to freedom of expression under the ECHR may be subject to limits if prescribed per law and proportional.¹²⁹ Rights under the CFR can also be limited as necessary, proportionate and provided by law in order to satisfy an objective of general interest for the EU or to protect the rights of others if the “essence” of the right is still respected.¹³⁰ Accordingly, not every breach of rights will be unlawful if it can be justified.¹³¹

¹¹⁹ See *Budischowsky*, Art 57 AEUV in Jäger/Stöger, EUV/AEUV para 8.

¹²⁰ See *Klamert*, EU-Recht² para 486 f.

¹²¹ Art 57 TFEU.

¹²² See Art 57 TFEU.

¹²³ See CJEU, 3. 12. 1974, 33/74, *Van Binsbergen*.

¹²⁴ See Art 18 TFEU; for further information see Chapter 3.3.3.

¹²⁵ See *Klamert*, EU-Recht² para 427.

¹²⁶ See Chapter 3.1.2.1.

¹²⁷ See *Öhlinger/Eberhrad*, *Verfassungsrecht*¹² (2019) para 694.

¹²⁸ See Art 2 and 3 ECHR.

¹²⁹ Art 10(2) ECHR.

¹³⁰ Art 52(1) CFR.

¹³¹ See C-507/17, *Google vs France*.

The CFR contains essential fundamental rights for the EU legal framework. Moreover, the rights under the ECHR form part of EU law as the EU is a party to the ECHR.¹³² The CFR and the ECHR cover very similar ground,¹³³ and their rights are interpreted similarly by the courts (ECJ and ECtHR).¹³⁴ The CFR applies to the actions of EU organs and institutions, as well as member states “when they are implementing Union law”.¹³⁵ The CFR therefore applies to member states when enforcing or implementing secondary law,¹³⁶ such as directives¹³⁷ and regulations.¹³⁸ The CFR also applies when market freedoms are violated by national laws.¹³⁹ The ECHR secures a range of fundamental rights and freedoms for individuals in signatory states¹⁴⁰ and establishes its own court, the ECtHR.¹⁴¹

European law has primacy of application over national constitutional laws.¹⁴² Accordingly, the CFR will apply instead of national rights regimes when member states apply “fully harmonized” EU law,¹⁴³ that must be implemented without discretion. However, when applying “partially harmonized” secondary law, member states often have discretion as to how to incorporate EU law into their domestic law. In these cases, the CJEU has acknowledged that national fundamental rights remain applicable if they ensure a higher protection level than the CFR.¹⁴⁴¹⁴⁵

Accordingly, the CFR is a minimum rights standard (in the case of partly harmonized EU law) for member states and domestic law cannot undermine the effectiveness of EU law.¹⁴⁶

3.1.4.1 Human Dignity (Art 1 CFR)

While human dignity is not explicitly mentioned in the ECHR,¹⁴⁷ the CFR states that “human dignity is inviolable” and must be “respected and protected”.¹⁴⁸ Human dignity is not only a right in itself, but functions as an interpretation maxim for other rights¹⁴⁹ and secondary law.¹⁵⁰

¹³² Art 2 TEU.

¹³³ Article 52(3) of the CFR provides that the meaning and scope of CFR rights that correspond to rights under the ECHR are to be the same as those ECHR rights.

¹³⁴ However, since the CJEU received jurisdiction under the CFR, “the proportion of cases in which the CJEU has drawn on the ECHR [...] has declined”; see *Craig/de Búrca*, EU law: text, cases, and materials⁶ (2015) 380.

¹³⁵ Art 51(1) CFR.

¹³⁶ See *Holoubek/Oswald*, Art 51 GRC, Anwendungsbereich in *Holoubek/Lienbacher* (eds) GRC-Kommentar² (2019), para 20.

¹³⁷ See C-74/95, *X*, para 25f; C-101/01, *Lindqvist*, para 87; C-275/06, *Promusicae*, para 68; C-314/12, *UPC Telekabel Wien GmbH*, para 42ff.

¹³⁸ See C-5/88, *Wach auf*, para 19; C-2/92, *Bostock*, para 16; C-15/95, *Earl de Kerlast*, para 36.

¹³⁹ See C-71/02, *Karner*; C-368/95, *Familiapress*.

¹⁴⁰ Art 1 ECHR.

¹⁴¹ Art 19 ECHR.

¹⁴² See C-11/70, *Internationale Handelsgesellschaft*, para 3; näher nur *Öhlinger/Potacs*, EU-Recht und staatliches Recht⁷ (2020) 88 f; but also see the German Constitutional Court *Recht auf Vergessen II*, 6.11.2019 Az. 1 BvR 276/17.

¹⁴³ Art 51 CFR. The Product Liability Directive is an example of a fully harmonized directive: see *Maňko*, EU competence in private law: The Treaty framework for a European private law and challenges for coherence (2015).

¹⁴⁴ See *Holoubek/Oswald*, Art 51 GRC, in *Holoubek/Lienbacher*, para 32. See also Art 53 CFR.

¹⁴⁵ C-399/11, *Melloni*, para 60; C-617/10; see also *Åkerberg Fransson*, para 29 and *Skouris*, Aspekte des Grundrechtsschutzes der Europäischen Union nach Lissabon, in *Leutheusser-Schnarrenberger* (eds), *Vom Recht auf Menschenwürde* (2013) 83 (92f).

¹⁴⁶ Case C-399/11 *Melloni vs Ministerio Fiscal*.

¹⁴⁷ See *Fuchs/Segalla*, Art 1 GRC, *Würde des Menschen* in *Holoubek/Lienbacher* (eds), GRC-Kommentar² (2019) para 13.

¹⁴⁸ Art 1 CFR.

¹⁴⁹ See Official Journal of the European Union, Explanations relating to the Charter of Fundamental Rights, 2007/C 303/02, Explanation on Article 1; *Haberkamm*, Die Auslegung der Richtlinie über unlautere Geschäftspraktiken im Lichte der europäischen Grundrechte (2013) 261.

¹⁵⁰ See *Fuchs/Segalla*, Art 1 GRC, para 38.

The extent to which human dignity is truly “inviolable” is subject to discussion.¹⁵¹ Since Art 52(1) CFR is applicable to all fundamental rights in the CFR and states that “any limitation on the exercise of the rights and freedoms recognized by this Charter must be provided for by law and respect the essence of those rights and freedoms”,¹⁵² human dignity may be just as violable as other CFR rights. Human dignity is also not defined in the CFR or the official Journal of the EU, making it difficult to determine the right’s material scope.

One way to attempt to define human dignity is to identify considerations that reflect the concept,¹⁵³ such as physical integrity, personal identity, individuality and equality.¹⁵⁴ These non-exhaustive considerations¹⁵⁵ provide a basis to understand the challenges of DTs for human dignity. DTs such as the “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” use case could raise issues for physical integrity, and this use case and the “Municipality Chatbot Kari” use case could both challenge the personal identity and associated dignity of human beings as they replace human services.¹⁵⁶ DTs such as the “Ethically Responsible Big Open Data” use case also pose challenges to individuality and personal identity if they collect large amounts of data and risk treating humans as data objects.¹⁵⁷ As discussed in relation to equality, DTs that use automated decision making could interfere with human dignity through their potential to magnify biases.¹⁵⁸ Accordingly, the right to human dignity raises several important considerations that should guide public administrations in whether and how they adopt DTs to avoid breaching this right.

3.1.4.2 Life (Art 2 CFR, Art 2 ECHR)

The right to life not only protects an individual from interferences by the state, but also obliges member states to guarantee an “effective protection of life”.¹⁵⁹ This right obliges the public administration to implement safety standards for the use of DTs if those could interfere with the right to life. The right to life could also contain an obligation to introduce DTs where they would effectively protect life themselves. Public administrations may also have transparency and information obligations deriving from this right.

An obligation to introduce DTs could arise in the medical sector, where constrained public resources and the need to ensure a certain “standard of care”¹⁶⁰ could be addressed through DTs.¹⁶¹ While the ECtHR has not explicitly stated an obligation to use technology to date, it has recognized that member states must take adequate legislative measures to ensure an adequate medical supply.¹⁶² It is therefore possible that member states could be required to ban outdated treatment methods by law.¹⁶³

Once member states have implemented a sufficient framework, the specifics of their health policy (e.g.: the conditions of the health service) are subject to their discretion.¹⁶⁴ According to the ECtHR, member states are not responsible for treatment errors¹⁶⁵ and are only accountable in “exceptional circumstances” such as “denial of

¹⁵¹ See C-341/05, *Laval* para 94; *Schwarzburg*, *Die Menschenwürde im Recht der Europäischen Union* (2011) 364 ff; *Fuchs/Segalla*, Art 1 GRC, para 43; compare *Haberkamm*, *Auslegung* 262.

¹⁵² Art 52 (1) CFR.

¹⁵³ Another approach would be to define Human dignity in a “positive” way see *Schwarzburg*, *Die Menschenwürde im Recht der Europäischen Union* (2012) 80 ff.

¹⁵⁴ See *Fuchs/Segalla*, Art 1 GRC, para 35.

¹⁵⁵ See *Fuchs/Segalla*, Art 1 GRC, para 36.

¹⁵⁶ See *Datteri/Tamburrini*, *Ethical Reflections on Health Care Robotics, Ethics and robotic* 2009, 1-14 (2).

¹⁵⁷ See *Aizenberg/Van den Hoven*, *Designing for human rights in AI, Big Data and Society* 2020, 1 (5).

¹⁵⁸ See *Ehrke-Rabel*, *Data* 311 f.

¹⁵⁹ See *Grabenwarter/Pabel*, *Europäische Menschenrechtskonvention*⁷ (2021) § 20. Fundamentalgarantien para 18.

¹⁶⁰ See *Schneeberger/Stöger/Holzinger*, *The European Legal Framework of Medical AI*, CD-MAKE 2020, 209 (211).

¹⁶¹ See European Commission, *State of Health in the EU*, Companion Report (2019) 9.

¹⁶² See ECtHR 12. 01. 2016, *Bilbija and Blažević vs Kroatien*, No. 62870/13, para 100.

¹⁶³ See *Schneeberger/Stöger/Holzinger*, CD-MAKE 2020, 209 (211).

¹⁶⁴ See *Grabenwarter/Pabel*, *EMRK*⁷ 178 f.

¹⁶⁵ See ECtHR 13. 11. 2012, *Z vs Poland*, No. 46132/08, para 76; ECtHR 04. 05. 2000, *Powell vs United Kingdom*, No. 45305/99.

access to life-saving emergency treatment”.¹⁶⁶ It is therefore unlikely that a right to treatment through DTs arises from the right to life. However, since the member states could be required to replace outdated treatment methods,¹⁶⁷ DTs might be a suitable replacement for those methods in certain areas.¹⁶⁸

Aside from a right to DTs, transparency obligations could derive from the obligation to protect life. The ECtHR has stated several times that Art 2 ECHR contains a duty of the state to inform affected persons about dangers to life.¹⁶⁹ In the cases *L.C.B.*¹⁷⁰ and *Öneryildiz*,¹⁷¹ the state had an obligation to actively inform affected persons about dangers on the basis of its duties to protect. The duty to inform about a dangerous situation has also arisen in connection with natural disasters, such as the *Budayeva*¹⁷² and *Kolyadenko*¹⁷³ cases. However, the threshold for triggering Art 2 ECHR is high,¹⁷⁴ and will usually only be reached when a death has occurred.¹⁷⁵

In the *McCann* case,¹⁷⁶ the ECtHR derived active information obligations from Art 2 ECHR and also imposed an obligation on the state to investigate and obtain information.¹⁷⁷ The ECtHR did not specify the extent of these “investigative” obligations, stating only that investigations and information gathering must be carried out in an effective manner.¹⁷⁸ However, the duty to investigate and obtain information forms part of the obligation to actively provide information,¹⁷⁹ and public administrations will need to be prepared to fulfil these obligations if considering the implementation of DTs that could carry a risk to life.

3.1.4.3 Private Life (Art 7 CFR, Article 8 ECHR)

The right to private life¹⁸⁰ stems from a pre-technological conception of the private sphere. It protects any information relating to an identified or identifiable individual,¹⁸¹ and extends beyond information relating to the sphere of the “home” to protect the right to establish and develop relationships with other human beings, including in a professional context.¹⁸² However, the right to privacy is subject to limits,¹⁸³ and a breach may be lawful if it is in accordance with the law, necessary and proportionate.

When it comes to using new technologies, the right is often interpreted broadly and any collation of personal data could be a breach of this right. For example, collection of personal information in a database has been held to be a breach of the right to privacy, regardless of how it is used (although the breach may be justified by the purpose

¹⁶⁶ See ECtHR 19. 12. 2017, *Lopes de Sousa Fernandes vs Portugal*, No. 56080/13, para 190.

¹⁶⁷ See *Schneeberger/Stöger/Holzinger*, CD-MAKE 2020, 209 (211).

¹⁶⁸ See European Commission, State 9.

¹⁶⁹ See ECtHR 09. 06. 1998, *L.C.B vs United Kingdom*, No. 14/1997/798/1001; ECtHR 30.11.2004, *Öneryildiz versus Turkey*; ECtHR 28.02.2012, *Kolyadenko vs Russia*, No. 17423/05, 20534/05, 20678/05, 23263/05, 24283/05, 35673/05; ECtHR *Budayeva ua vs Russia*, No. 15339/02, 21166/02, 20058/02, 11673/02, 15343/02.

¹⁷⁰ See ECtHR 09. 06. 1998, *L.C.B vs United Kingdom*, No. 14/1997/798/1001, para 38 f.

¹⁷¹ See ECtHR 30. 11.2004, *Öneryildiz vs Turkey*, No. 48939/99, para 89 f.

¹⁷² See ECtHR 20.03.2008, *Budayeva ua vs Russia*, No. 15339/02, 21166/02, 20058/02, 11673/02, 15343/02, para 131.

¹⁷³ See ECtHR 28. 02. 2012, *Kolyadenko vs Russia*, No. 17423/05, 20534/05, 20678/05, 23263/05, 24283/05, 35673/05, para 159.

¹⁷⁴ See *Braig*, *Umweltschutz durch die Europäische Menschenrechtskonvention* (2013) 288.

¹⁷⁵ See *Schlüter*, *Beweisfragen in der Rechtsprechung des Europäischen Gerichtshofs für Menschenrechte* (2019) 151.

¹⁷⁶ See ECtHR 27 .09. 1995, *McCann vs United Kingdom*, No. 18984/91.

¹⁷⁷ See ECtHR 27. 09. 1995, *McCann vs United Kingdom*, No. 18984/91, para 161.

¹⁷⁸ See ECtHR 27. 09. 1995, *McCann vs United Kingdom*, No. 18984/91, para 162.

¹⁷⁹ See *Schlüter*, *Beweisfragen* 167.

¹⁸⁰ Art 7 CFR, Art 8 ECHR.

¹⁸¹ See C-311/13, *Data Protection Commissioner v Facebook Ireland Limited and Maximillian Schrems* CJEU Case C-311/13, para 170.

¹⁸² See ECtHR 16. 2. 2000, *Amann vs Switzerland*, No. 27798/95, para 65.

¹⁸³ See ECHR Art 8(2); CFR Art 52; C-311/13, *Data Protection Commissioner vs Facebook Ireland Limited and Maximillian Schrems*, para 172. The CFR right has been held to be subject to the same limits as the ECHR right: see C-92/09 and C-93/09, *Volker und Markus Schecke GbR and Hartmut Eifert vs Land Hessen* , para 52.

of collection and safeguards).¹⁸⁴ DTs like the “Ethically Responsible Big Open Data” use case that gather large amounts of data will therefore engage privacy concerns from the moment of collection. Data already in the public domain can also still attract privacy rights if it is compiled in a manner or degree beyond that which is normally foreseeable.¹⁸⁵ The right to privacy also extends beyond “sensitive” personal data, capturing the right to develop relationships with other human beings in non-private contexts. Accordingly, whether information is “sensitive” or not will not always be determinative in an assessment of whether an interference with private life has occurred.¹⁸⁶

Sometimes, the requirement for adequate safeguards such as timely deletion can outweigh a legitimate objective. For example, in the *Digital Rights Ireland* case, the CJEU held that the right to privacy required safeguards on the collection and storage of data such as deletion after a certain period, even though the Court accepted the collection of data had a legitimate objective.¹⁸⁷

Accordingly, public administrations need to be acutely conscious of the right to privacy and only use data as necessary for and proportionate to a legitimate objective, ensuring appropriate safeguards are in place. In the context of DTs, public administrations should avoid “technology solutionism”¹⁸⁸, where a technology is adopted because it is (for example) effective at a public administration task, but it is not *necessary* or proportionate to adopt that technology in order to complete the task to an acceptable standard. Public administrations should also be conscious of their obligations towards employees when considering introducing DTs that involve the use of employee data (such as the “Ethically Responsible Big Open Data” use case), as data relating to employees has been held to attract privacy rights.¹⁸⁹

Beyond the limits on state interference with privacy rights, the state also has positive obligations to ensure effective protection of private life.¹⁹⁰ These can extend to obligations to pass laws that enable prosecution and identification of those responsible for data breaches¹⁹¹ and obligations to provide transparent information about DTs to people who may be impacted by them. As outlined above, this obligation also arises from the right to life.¹⁹² However, where life is not endangered, this obligation can still arise in connection to the right to private and family life.¹⁹³

For example, in the *Guerra* case,¹⁹⁴ the competent authorities failed to inform affected persons about the health risk potential of a chemical plant.¹⁹⁵ The ECtHR derived extensive information obligations from the right to private and family life,¹⁹⁶ finding that severe environmental pollution could prevent people from enjoying their private and family life, and that Art 8 ECHR had been violated, as the state should have provided the affected persons with information about the pollution and enabled them to assess the risk.¹⁹⁷

Overall, the right to privacy carries several obligations for public administrations involved in the implementation of DTs. While interference is likely to be lawful where it is in accordance with the law and deemed necessary when it is connected to a legitimate aim such as public safety, many DTs will not reach this threshold. Public

¹⁸⁴ See ECtHR 26.3.1987, *Leander vs Sweden*, Nr 9248/81, para 48.

¹⁸⁵ See ECtHR 27.06.2017, *Satakunnan Markkinapörssi Oy and Satamedia Oy vs Finland*, No. 931/13, para 133 ff.)

¹⁸⁶ See ECtHR 16.02.2000, *Amann vs Switzerland*, No. 27798/95, para 70.

¹⁸⁷ See C 293/12, *Digital Rights vs Ireland*.

¹⁸⁸ See *Pollicino*, “Getting the Future Right – Artificial Intelligence and Fundamental Rights”, A view from the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, *BioLaw Journal – Rivista di BioDiritto*, n. 1/2021.

¹⁸⁹ See ECtHR 5.9.2017, *Bărbulescu vs Romania*, No. 61496/08; ECtHR 22.2.2018 *Libert v. France*, No. 588/13; ECtHR 28.11.2017, *Antović and Mirković vs Montenegro* No. 70838/13.

¹⁹⁰ See for example, ECtHR 9.01.2018, *López Ribalda and others vs Spain*, No. 1874/13 and 8567/13, para 60f.

¹⁹¹ See ECtHR 2.12.2008, *K.U. v. Finland*, No. 2872/02; ECtHR 12.11.2013, *Söderman vs Sweden*, No. 5786/08.)

¹⁹² See ECtHR 5.12.2013, *Vilnes ua vs Norway*, No. 52806/09, 22703/10.

¹⁹³ See ECtHR 5.12.2013, *Vilnes ua vs Norway*, No. 52806/09, 22703/10, para 234.

¹⁹⁴ See ECtHR 19.2.1998, *Guerra ua vs Italy*, No. 116/1996/735/932.

¹⁹⁵ See ECtHR 19.2.1998, *Guerra ua vs Italy*, No. 116/1996/735/932, para 12 ff.

¹⁹⁶ See ECtHR 19.2.1998, *Guerra ua vs Italy*, No. 116/1996/735/932 para 55 ff.

¹⁹⁷ See ECtHR 19.2.1998, *Guerra ua vs Italy*, No. 116/1996/735/932 para 60.

administrations must avoid arbitrary interference with privacy rights and ensure adequate measures are in place to protect individuals' privacy against interference from others. In some cases, public administrations will also need to provide information about DTs to enable citizens to assess risks and make decisions about their private lives.

3.1.4.4 Data Protection (Art 16 TFEU, Art 8 CFR)

The right to data protection¹⁹⁸ is similar to the right to privacy, and has been held to be subject to the same limits as the right to privacy under the ECHR.¹⁹⁹ However, it is a distinct and "more modern" right,²⁰⁰ and has a specific focus on the protection of data about an individual in the information society.²⁰¹ This right and the right to privacy also overlap considerably with data rights under the GDPR, which we explore as part of secondary law below. As the GDPR is a fully harmonized regulation, the right to data protection under Art 8 CFR is binding on member states whenever they act in relation to data protection.

The CJEU has become more protective of data rights in recent years, striking down EU legislation for violating fundamental data rights.²⁰² For example, a data retention directive was found to be invalid as it required communications providers to keep citizens' telecommunications data for up to two years without adequate safeguards.²⁰³

The right to data protection is particularly relevant in the context of DTs, as these technologies often use large amounts of personal or other data and carry new risks of data breaches or loss. Large amounts of data often also serve as the source of learning material for DTs. For example, the "Municipality Chatbot Kari" and "Robot-mediated rehabilitation" use cases may both involve the collection of data which is then used for further training or other applications.

To comply with the right to data protection, public administrations must process personal data fairly, for specified purposes, and on the basis of consent or a legitimate basis laid down by law.²⁰⁴ Individuals also have rights of access to collected data concerning them and to have it rectified,²⁰⁵ and an independent authority must control compliance with these rules.²⁰⁶ Further, communicating personal data to a third party is an interference with the right to data protection, as is the "retention of personal data and access to that data with a view to its use by public authorities, irrespective of whether the information in question relating to private life is sensitive or whether the persons concerned have been inconvenienced in any way on account of that interference".²⁰⁷ As the ETAPAS use cases all involve the collection of personal data, public administrations must ensure they comply with these requirements as well as those in the GDPR (outlined in Chapter 3.2.1).

3.1.4.5 Freedom of Expression (Art 11 CFR, Art 10 ECHR)

Freedom of expression includes the freedom to express one's opinion and to receive information and ideas.²⁰⁸ We consider this right mostly in the context of misinformation, as the right is increasingly considered as both a shield against and a mechanism for the dissemination of false information. In the context of the ETAPAS misinformation detector use case, the right to freedom of expression could prevent or limit public administrations' ability to use

¹⁹⁸ Art 8 CFR.

¹⁹⁹ See C-92/09 and C-93/09, *Volker und Markus Schecke GbR and Hartmut Eifert vs Land Hessen*, para 52.

²⁰⁰ See C-92/09 and C-93/02, *Volker und Markus Schecke GbR vs Land Hessen*, Opinion of Advocate General Sharpston, para. 71

²⁰¹ See European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, Handbook on European Data Protection Law. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union (2018); *Ehrke-Rabel*, Data 297.

²⁰² See C-92-93/09, *Volker und Markus Schecke GbR vs Land Hessen*; Case C-293/12, *Digital Rights Ireland vs Minister for Communications*.

²⁰³ See C-293/12, *Digital Rights Ireland vs Minister for Communications*.

²⁰⁴ Art 8(1) CFR; see C-311/13, *Data Protection Commissioner vs Facebook Ireland Limited and Maximillian Schrems*, para 170.

²⁰⁵ Art 8(2) CFR.

²⁰⁶ Art 8(3).

²⁰⁷ See C-311/13, *Data Protection Commissioner vs Facebook Ireland Limited and Maximillian Schrems*, para 171.

²⁰⁸ See *Öhlinger/Eberhard*, *Verfassungsrecht*¹² 426.

DTs or other tools to flag, control or remove misinformation. The right to freedom of expression also raises potential transparency obligations under Art 10 ECHR and Art 11 CFR.

False information has been spread throughout history,²⁰⁹ but the internet and especially social media platforms have led to a rise of published false and harmful information²¹⁰ as “news” is no longer constrained to traditional media outlets.²¹¹ The ECtHR has acknowledged this problem:

“The electronic network, serving billions of users worldwide, is not and potentially will never be subject to the same regulations and control. The risk of harm posed by content and communications on the Internet to the exercise and enjoyment of human rights and freedoms, particularly the right to respect for private life, is certainly higher than that posed by the press. Therefore, the policies governing reproduction of material from the printed media and the Internet may differ. The latter undeniably have to be adjusted according to the technology’s specific features in order to secure the protection and promotion of the rights and freedoms concerned.”²¹²

The right to freedom of expression includes the right “to impart information and ideas”.²¹³ Freedom of speech itself does not forbid the dissemination of false information.²¹⁴ An interference with the right can occur when an individual is subject to “formalities, conditions, restrictions or penalties” by the state.²¹⁵ If the public administration uses DTs to remove information which could be accessed, made publicly available, or communicated by individuals, there is likely an interference with the right to freedom of expression. However, the right is qualified maybe lawfully violated if the violation is proportionate and prescribed by law.²¹⁶

Moreover, the ECtHR differentiates between statements of fact and value judgements when there is an interference with freedom of speech:²¹⁷ while factual statements can be proven right or wrong, ideas or value judgements cannot.²¹⁸ Therefore, statements could require a factual basis to be proven,²¹⁹ but value judgements cannot require proof of the truth of a statement, and the right to freedom of speech is likely to be violated if it is required.²²⁰ Nevertheless, not all interferences in value judgements are per se disproportionate and an interference may be

²⁰⁹ See *Sardo*, Categories, Balancing, and Fake News: The Jurisprudence of the European Court of Human Rights, *Canadian Journal of Law & Jurisprudence* XXXIII 2020, 435-460 (445).

²¹⁰ See *Martens/Aguiar/Gomez-Herrera/Mueller-Langer*, The digital transformation of news media and the rise of disinformation and fake news (2018) <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/eur-scientific-and-technical-research-reports/digital-transformation-news-media-and-rise-disinformation-and-fake-news> (last downloaded on the 28th of April 2021).

²¹¹ See *Neuwirth*, The Global Regulation of “Fake News” in the Time of Oxymora: Facts and Fictions about the Covid-19 Pandemic as Coincidences or Predictive Programming?, *International Journal for the Semiotics of Law*, 2021.

²¹² ECtHR 5. 5. 2011, *Shtekel vs Ukraine*, No. 33014/05, para 63.

²¹³ Art 10 ECHR, Art 11 CFR.

²¹⁴ See ECtHR 6. 9. 2005, *Salov vs Ukraine*, No. 65518/01, para 113; ECtHR, 25.7.2019, *Brzeziński vs Poland*, No. 47542/07, 25/07/2019; *Harris/O’Boyle/Warbrick*, Law of the European Convention on Human Rights⁴ (2018) 445.

²¹⁵ Art 10(2) ECHR.

²¹⁶ Art 10(2) ECHR and Art 52(1) CFR.

²¹⁷ See ECtHR 15. 3. 2011, *Otegi Mondragon vs Spain*, No. 2034/07 para 53; ECtHR, 2. 11. 2006, *Ruokanen vs Finland*, No. 45130/06, para 41; ECtHR 1. 12. 2009, *Karsai vs Hungary*, No. 5380/07, para 23; ECtHR 8. 7. 1986, *Lingens vs Austria*, No. 9815/82, para 46.

²¹⁸ See ECtHR 8. 7. 1986, *Lingens vs Austria*, No. 9815/82, para 46; *Grabenwarter/Frank*, Bundes-Verfassungsgesetz und Grundrechte B-VG, Art 10 EMRK. Freiheit der Meinungsäußerung (2020) para 12; *Muzak*, Bundes-Verfassungsrecht B-VG, Art 10 EMRK. Freiheit der Meinungsäußerung (2020) para 14.

²¹⁹ See ECtHR 23. 11. 2017, *Standard Verlags GmbH vs Austria*, No. 19068/13 and 73322/13, *Muzak*, Art 10 EMRK para 14.

²²⁰ See ECtHR 8. 7. 1986, *Lingens vs Austria*, No. 9815/82, para 46.

justified if the idea is completely lacking a factual basis, excessive,²²¹ or promotes ideas “contrary to the text and spirit of the Convention”.²²²

Accordingly, the use of DTs to moderate or regulate misinformation may be permissible where misinformation has been restricted by law. However, DTs would need to be able to differentiate between statements of fact and value judgements, and to assess the acceptability of certain value judgement. Such an assessment would need to be carried out on a case by case basis and is likely to be difficult to achieve through automated means, so human involvement would likely be required.

Since freedom of expression does not only protect the freedom to express one’s own opinion, but also to receive news and ideas,²²³ the public administration may also be subject to transparency and information obligations when implementing DTs. The ECtHR has been hesitant to acknowledge an obligation on member states to take active steps to provide information, finding that:²²⁴

“Article 10 does not, in circumstances such as those of the present case, confer on the individual a right of access to a register containing information on his personal position, nor does it embody an obligation on the Government to impart such information to the individual.”²²⁵

However, the ECtHR did confine its finding in this case to the circumstances of the individual case,²²⁶ so it is possible that an obligation to provide information exists in other contexts.²²⁷ A resolution of the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe points to the possibility of an active information obligation for states deriving from Art 10 ECHR:

“This right [referring to the right to freedom of expression] shall include freedom to seek, receive, impart, publish and distribute information and ideas. There shall be a corresponding duty for the public authorities to make available information on matters of public interest within reasonable limits [...]”²²⁸

While this possibility is yet to be clarified, the right to freedom of expression may develop similarly to the rights to life and privacy and be interpreted as creating obligations on the state to actively provide or make available certain information to citizens.

3.2 Secondary Law

While some secondary laws cover all matters in a legal field (horizontal effect), others are only concerned with certain specific legal areas (vertical effect).

An example of secondary law with horizontal effect is the GDPR.²²⁹ The GDPR is particularly relevant for the implementation of DTs, since all or most DTs (including our use cases) involve processing personal data and therefore raise questions regarding data protection. Accordingly, we examine the GDPR in detail in this section.

²²¹ See ECtHR 12. 1. 2016, *Genner vs Austria*, No. 55495/08, para 46; ECtHR 27. 2. 2001, *Jerusalem v. Austria*, no. 26958/95, para 43, *Grabenwarter/Frank*, Art 10 EMRK para 12.

²²² ECtHR 15. 3. 2011, *Otegi Mondragon vs Spain*, No. 2034/07 para 55.

²²³ See *Öhlinger/Eberhard*, *Verfassungsrecht*¹² 426.

²²⁴ See ECtHR 15.06.2004, *Sirbu vs Moldova*, Nr 73562/01, 73565/01, 73712/01, 73744/01, 73972/01, 73973/01; ECtHR 26.3.1987, *Leander vs Sweden*, Nr 9248/81, para 74.

²²⁵ ECtHR 26.3.1987, *Leander vs Sweden*, Nr 9248/81, para 74.

²²⁶ See *Van Rijn*, Freedom of Expression, in: Van Dijk/Van Hoof/Van Rijn/Zwaak (eds) *Theory and Practice of the European Convention on Human Rights*⁵ (2018) 787.

²²⁷ See *Van Rijn*, Freedom 787.

²²⁸ Parliamentary Assembly, Declaration on mass communication media and Human Rights, Resolution 428 (1970), para 8.

²²⁹ Regulation 2016/679/EU.

Since product law regulations are closely linked to the product itself, there are several vertical product laws. Several directives and regulations could be relevant to DTs, such as the Low Voltage Directive,²³⁰ Machinery Directive,²³¹ Medical Devices Regulation,²³² Radio Equipment Directive,²³³ Electromagnetic Compatibility Directive,²³⁴ and the Safety and Health at Work Framework Directive^{235, 236} However, in order to provide an overview of the framework applicable to (almost) all DTs, we focus on two horizontal product laws and the issues DTs may pose for them: the General Product Safety Directive (GPSD)²³⁷ and the Product Liability Directive (PLD).²³⁸

Equality directives such as the Race Equality Directive,²³⁹ the Directive on Equal Treatment in Employment and Occupation,²⁴⁰ and the Directives on Equal Treatment Between Men and Women in Relation to Employment and Access to Goods and Services²⁴¹ are also discussed in this section as they are particularly relevant for the implementation of DTs that could treat different groups unequally.

In this section, we also discuss the European Commission's Proposal for a Regulation on a European approach for Artificial Intelligence²⁴² ("proposed AI Regulation"). While the proposed AI Regulation is a non-binding proposal and does not form part of the binding EU legal framework, we note it here as a potential cornerstone of the future EU legal framework for DTs that would apply to public administrations. The proposed risk-based approach also signals the likely path of future regulation, which we explore more in our conclusions.

Depending on the role of the public administration and the legal area, public procurement and state aid laws could also be relevant. However, since the role of the state is not determined yet in most use cases, these laws will be examined further in ETAPAS Deliverables 4.2-4.5.

3.2.1 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

There is a close link between the fundamental rights to data protection and private life and the GDPR. The GDPR holds that "the protection of natural persons in relation to the processing of personal data is a fundamental right".²⁴³ It²⁴⁴ aims to increase transparency by making the processing of personal data

²³⁰ Directive 2014/35/EC.

²³¹ Directive 2006/42/EC.

²³² Directive 93/42/EC.

²³³ Directive 2014/53/EU.

²³⁴ Directive 2014/30/EU.

²³⁵ Directive 89/391 EEC.

²³⁶ See European Commission, EU product safety framework for advanced robots & autonomous systems https://ec.europa.eu/information_society/newsroom/image/document/2017-30/felicia_stoica_the_existing_eu_safety_framework_with_regard_to_autonomous_systems_and_advanced_robots_robots_6210B836-9707-D592-D33613EE1C6F086A_46145.pdf (last downloaded on the 20th of April 2021); European Parliament, Safety issues, Legal aspects regarding safety <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/infographics/robotics/public/concern/safety-issues.html> (last downloaded on the 20th of April 2021).

²³⁷ Directive 2001/95/EC.

²³⁸ Directive 85/374/EEC.

²³⁹ Directive 2000/43/EC.

²⁴⁰ Directive 2000/78/EC.

²⁴¹ Directive 2004/113/EC.

²⁴² COM (2021) 206 final.

²⁴³ Recital 1 GDPR.

²⁴⁴ See Art 5(1)(a) GDPR.

both visible and comprehensible to the data subject.²⁴⁵ The GDPR also aims to implement the principles of fairness and lawfulness²⁴⁶ and accountability for data processing.²⁴⁷

The GDPR applies to all “natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data”.²⁴⁸ This means that only natural persons (and not legal persons) are protected by the GDPR,²⁴⁹ and that they are only protected if personal data is being processed. The term “personal data” is defined in Art 4(1) GDPR to mean “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person”.²⁵⁰ The GDPR is not usually applicable when anonymized data is being processed,²⁵¹ unless that data can be deanonymized and traced back to an individual. As the line between personal and anonymized data can be blurred,²⁵² the analysis of the GDPR’s applicability is contextually dependent on a case by case basis. Public administrations should not assume that “anonymous” data cannot be linked to an identifiable individual (for example, in the “Ethically Responsible Big Open Data” use case).

Following our overview in Chapter 3.1.4 of fundamental rights to privacy and data protection and the importance of transparency and safeguards for the use of DTs, we now examine specific provisions of the GDPR that implement these rights and obligations into concrete law: the duty to provide information,²⁵³ the right to access information,²⁵⁴ the right to data erasure or “the right to be forgotten”,²⁵⁵ several safeguards for the data subject when automated decisions are made,²⁵⁶ the right to an explanation of automated decision-making,²⁵⁷ privacy by design,²⁵⁸ and data impact assessments²⁵⁹.

3.2.1.1 Duty to Provide Information (Arts 13 and 14, Recitals 60 ff) & Right to Access Information (Art 15 GDPR and Recital 63)

The GDPR regulates what information the controller must provide to a data subject when data is collected from that data subject²⁶⁰ and when it is collected from someone else.²⁶¹ The information includes “the identity and the

²⁴⁵ See Article 29 Data Protection Working Group, Guidelines on Automated individual decision-making and Profiling for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, WP251rev.01 (2018) 9 f.

²⁴⁶ Art 5(1)(a) GDPR.

²⁴⁷ Art 5(2) GDPR.

²⁴⁸ Art 1 GDPR.

²⁴⁹ See *Lachmayer*, Art 1 DSGVO, Gegenstand und Ziele in Knyrim (eds), *DatKomm* (2018) para 30.

²⁵⁰ Art 4 (1) GDPR.

²⁵¹ See *Buocz/Ehrke-Rabel/Hödl/Eisenberger*, Bitcoin and the GDPR, *CLSR* 2018, 182 (186); *Lachmayer*, Art 1 DSGVO, para 31.

²⁵² See *Lachmayer*, Art 1 DSGVO, para 31.

²⁵³ Arts 13 and 14 GDPR, Recitals 60 ff.

²⁵⁴ Art 15 GDPR and Recital 63 GDPR.

²⁵⁵ Art 17 GDPR.

²⁵⁶ Art 22 GDPR, Recitals 71 f GDPR.

²⁵⁷ Compare *Wachter/Floridi/Mittelstadt*, Why a Right to Explanation of Automated Decision-Making Does Not Exist in the General Data Protection Regulation, *International Data Privacy Law*, 2017, 1 (1 ff); see *Schneeberger/Stöger/Holzinger*, CD-MAKE 2020, 209 (212 ff); *Brkan*, Do algorithms rule the world? Algorithmic decision-making and data protection in the framework of the GDPR and beyond, *International Journal of Law and Information Technology* 2019, 91; *Brkan/Bonnet*, Legal and technical feasibility of the GDPR’s quest for explanation of algorithmic decisions: of black boxes, white boxes and Fata Morganas, *European Journal Risk Regulation* 2020, 18; *Kaminski*, The right to explanation, explained. *Berkeley Technology Law Journal* 2019, 189; *Goodman/Flaxman*, European Union regulations on algorithmic decision-making and a “right to explanation”, *AI Magazine*, 2017, 50.

²⁵⁸ Art 25 GDPR.

²⁵⁹ Art 35 GDPR.

²⁶⁰ Art 13(1) GDPR; see *Eisenberger/Hödl/Huber/Lachmayer/Mittermüller*, Smart Farming - Rechtliche Perspektiven, *Jahrbuch Agrarrecht* (2017) 222.

²⁶¹ (Art 13(1) GDPR.

contact details of the controller”,²⁶² “the purposes of the processing for which the personal data are intended as well as the legal basis for the processing”,²⁶³ and “the recipients” of the processed data²⁶⁴. Alongside the duty of a controller to provide information, the data subject also has a right to access information such as the purposes of processing,²⁶⁵ the envisaged period of storage of criteria used to determine that period²⁶⁶ and any recipients of the processed data.²⁶⁷

In addition to this basic information, the controller must provide further information when automated decision making (ADM) is involved.²⁶⁸ The controller must inform that, ADM is being used. Moreover, the data subject has the right to request further information in the case of ADM.²⁶⁹ ADM arises in many DTs, such as the ETAPAS “Municipality Chatbot Kari” use case. In such a case the controller must provide information that ADM is occurring (such as a pop-up informing the user that an automated chatbot is operating without human oversight), meaningful information about the logic involved (such as the criteria used to identify, classify, and prioritize information), and the significance of processing and envisaged consequences for the individual (such as the use of personal information to determine what information is provided).²⁷⁰

In performing its informational obligations, the controller must also comply with Art 12 GDPR, which provides that information must be “concise, transparent, intelligible and [in an] easily accessible form, using clear and plain language”.²⁷¹

3.2.1.2 Right To Be Forgotten (Art 17 GDPR)

The “right to be forgotten” was first recognized as part of the EU legal framework in the landmark *Google Spain* case,²⁷² before being codified to some extent through the GDPR. In its interpretation of data protection rights in the EU, the CJEU found that data subjects have a right to request a search engine to de-reference data (by removing links from search results).²⁷³ The scope of this right was later found to be territorially limited to the EU, so search engines are not required to remove links from versions outside the EU.²⁷⁴

Following that case, the GDPR introduced a right of the data subject to obtain erasure of personal data without undue delay on certain grounds, such as where the data subject has withdrawn their consent and there is no other lawful basis for processing.²⁷⁵ Controllers must also take reasonable measures to inform all other controllers that links to or copies of the data must be erased.²⁷⁶ As DTs often involve linking or collating large amounts of personal data, public administrations should have built-in capabilities to respond to and action erasure requests promptly. However, these rights and obligations do not apply in some situations, such as where processing is necessary to exercise the right of freedom of expression and information, for reasons of public interest in the area of public health, or for archiving purposes in the public interest.²⁷⁷

²⁶² Art 13 (1) lit a GDPR; Art 14 (1) lit a GDPR.

²⁶³ Art 13 (1) lit c GDPR; Art 14 (1) lit c GDPR.

²⁶⁴ Art 13 (1) lit e GDPR; Art 14 (1) lit e GDPR.

²⁶⁵ Art 15 (1) lit a GDPR.

²⁶⁶ Art 15 (1) lit d GDPR.

²⁶⁷ Art 15 (1) lit c GDPR.

²⁶⁸ Art 13 (1) lit f GDPR; Art 14 no. 1 lit g GDPR; see *Schneeberger/Stöger/Holzinger*, CD-MAKE 2020, 209 (214).

²⁶⁹ Art 15 (1) lit h GDPR.

²⁷⁰ Art 13 no. 1 lit f GDPR; Art 14 no. 1 lit g GDPR.

²⁷¹ Art 12 (1) lit f GDPR.

²⁷² C-131/12, *Google vs Spain*.

²⁷³ See C-131/12, *Google vs Spain*.

²⁷⁴ See C-507/17, *Google vs France*.

²⁷⁵ Art 17(1) GDPR.

²⁷⁶ Art 17(2) GDPR.

²⁷⁷ Art 17(3) GDPR.

3.2.1.3 Safeguards against Automated-Decision-Making (Art 22 GDPR, Recitals 71 f)

Art 22 GDPR contains particular safeguards for data subjects when controllers are engaging in ADM. Firstly, it limits the types of ADM that can lawfully take place. Data subjects have the right not to be subject to a decision which is solely based on automated processing and which produces legal or similarly significant effects concerning an individual.²⁷⁸ The aim of this provision is that humans should not be treated as mere objects by machines²⁷⁹ and have resort to human alternatives where ADM takes place. However, it is not a blanket prohibition on all forms of ADM.

The term “decision” has a wide meaning²⁸⁰ and also includes “measures”.²⁸¹ If there is no decision being made (e.g.: when a situation is simply being assessed without consequences), Art 22 GDPR will not be applicable.²⁸² Moreover, the decision must be *solely* based on automated processing, so if there is any human involvement in the ADM process, the prohibition on ADM may not apply.²⁸³ For example, if the “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” use case involves machine-generated treatment decisions, but these decisions are subject to review and authorization by a medical practitioner, the decisions would not be considered ADM and would not fall under the Art 22 requirements.

The threshold for legal or similarly significant effects is also subject to interpretation. In the “Public Organizations Multi-factor Misinformation Handling” use case, the threshold of having legal effects on an individual would almost certainly be reached as the individual’s rights of free access to and expression of information would be affected under Art 10 ECHR and Art 11 CFR. “Similarly significant” effects, however, are more difficult to determine and a range of effects may be caught by this definition that fall short of having legal consequences for the individual.²⁸⁴

Even where a decision is solely based on ADM and has legal or similar effects, there are exceptions where the prohibition does not apply: where ADM is necessary for a contract between the data subject and a data controller,²⁸⁵ authorized by law which has suitable safeguards to protect the data subject,²⁸⁶ or on the basis of the data subject’s explicit consent.²⁸⁷ Where the contract or consent exceptions apply, controllers may only carry out ADM if they ensure adequate safeguards are in place,²⁸⁸ including a right to obtain human intervention, to express the data subject’s point of view and to contest the decision. Moreover, Recital 71, which is non-binding, contains a right to obtain an “explanation of the decision reached after such assessment”.

3.2.1.4 Right to Explanation?

The degree to which a data subject can actually obtain an explanation of decisions based on automated processing under the GDPR is subject to debate. As outlined above, data subjects have rights to access and receive certain information about automated decision-making and certain safeguards must be in place. However, these protections are unlikely to give rise to a right to explanation of a *specific* automated decision (such as a decision to take down a particular piece flagged as misinformation), and instead are likely to be limited to a right to an explanation of the system logic and “envisaged”, rather than actual, consequences for the individual.²⁸⁹ While

²⁷⁸ Art 22 (1) GDPR.

²⁷⁹ See *Schneeberger/Stöger/Holzinger*, CD-MAKE 2020, 209 (212).

²⁸⁰ See *Haidinger*, Art 22 DSGVO. Automatisierte Entscheidungen im Einzelfall einschließlich Profiling (2018) para 18.

²⁸¹ See Recital 71, sentence 1 GDPR.

²⁸² See *Haidinger*, Art 22 DSGVO, para 18.

²⁸³ *Wachter/Floridi/Mittelstadt*, International Data Privacy Law, 2017, 1; *Schneeberger/Stöger/Holzinger*, CD-MAKE 2020, 209 (212).

²⁸⁴ *Wachter/Floridi/Mittelstadt*, International Data Privacy Law, 2017, 1.

²⁸⁵ Art 22(2)(a).

²⁸⁶ Art 22(2)(b).

²⁸⁷ Art 22(2)(c).

²⁸⁸ Art 22(3).

²⁸⁹ *Wachter/Floridi/Mittelstadt*, International Data Privacy Law, 2017, 1.

Recital 71 does appear to envisage a right to an explanation of specific decisions, this is a non-binding part of the GDPR and serves as an aid to interpretation rather than a source of binding rights itself.

Despite these limitations, the various informational rights under the GDPR still oblige controllers and processors to be able to explain their systems in an accessible, understandable and meaningful form to data subjects.²⁹⁰ Public administrations adopting DTs that involve solely automated decisions that have individual consequences should be prepared to “translate” the logic of these technologies to provide system explanations to data subjects. Where a system’s decision-making process is protected by intellectual property rights or not comprehensible, an alternate translation of the logic may be used that must be comprehensible to the data subject. For example, the use of counterfactuals may be used as a proxy for a system explanation.²⁹¹

Transparency is also a particular concern where the public administration looks to create public-private partnerships with private entities who use proprietary algorithms. Here, the public administration must ensure it has sufficient understanding and oversight of these algorithms. Otherwise, as a publicly accountable entity, the administration risks being in breach of the GDPR and of being perceived as “hollowed out, dumb and dark” while private contractors perform public functions without scrutiny.²⁹²

3.2.1.5 Privacy by Design (Art 25 GDPR, Recital 78)

The GDPR also ensures data protection through the concepts of privacy by design and privacy by default (Art 25 GDPR). The aim is to use technology as a means of enforcing data protection law by designing data processing in a privacy-friendly way²⁹³ and using privacy-friendly default settings.²⁹⁴ These requirements place obligations on public administrations at the development and implementation stages of DTs to ensure they are designed to protect privacy from the outset.

Art 25(1) GDPR states that the controller must take “technical and organizational measures” to implement data protection principles such as data minimization in an effective manner. To determine which technical and organizational measures have to be taken, the controller must carry out a proportionality test²⁹⁵ considering “the nature, scope, context and purposes” of the data processing.²⁹⁶

The “nature” of data is concerned with what kind of data is being processed, especially whether it is sensitive.²⁹⁷ The “scope” is the quantity of data being processed.²⁹⁸ For example, the “Ethically Responsible Big Open Data” use case involving the data of more than 2.2 million public servants would require more protective measures than a database containing a small amount of personal information. The “context” is the circumstances of the data processing,²⁹⁹ such as how personal data are collected, whether the data subject has consented, and how the data processing is technically implemented (e.g.: local storage or cloud environment).³⁰⁰ Moreover, the “purpose” of the data processing will affect the proportionality of processing. Purposes such as human resources or health, as in the ETAPAS use cases, would require more privacy by design measures than mere address or telephone number administration systems.³⁰¹

²⁹⁰ Art 12.

²⁹¹ Compare *Wachter/Floridi/Mittelstadt*, *International Data Privacy Law*, 2017, 1.

²⁹² *Brauneis/Goodman*, *Algorithmic Transparency for the Smart City* 20 *Yale Journal of Law & Technology* 2018, 103.

²⁹³ See *Hötendorfer/Kastelitz/Tschohl*, *Art 25 DSGVO Datenschutz durch Technikgestaltung und durch datenschutzfreundliche Voreinstellungen* in Knyrim (eds), *DatKomm* (2018) para 4.

²⁹⁴ See *Hötendorfer/Kastelitz/Tschohl*, in Knyrim (eds) *Art 25 DSGVO* para 39.

²⁹⁵ Art 25(1) GDPR.

²⁹⁶ Art 25(1) GDPR.

²⁹⁷ See *Pollirer*, *Art 32 DSGVO, Sicherheit der Verarbeitung* in Knyrim (eds), *DatKomm* (2018) para 23.

²⁹⁸ See *Pollirer*, in Knyrim (eds) *Art 32 DSGVO* para 23.

²⁹⁹ See *Pollirer*, in Knyrim (eds) *Art 32 DSGVO* para 24.

³⁰⁰ See *Pollirer*, in Knyrim (eds) *Art 32 DSGVO* para 24.

³⁰¹ See *Pollirer*, in Knyrim (eds) *Art 32 DSGVO* para 25.

As well as the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing,³⁰² the required level of privacy by design measures depends on the state of the art, the risks for rights and freedoms and the costs of implementing the measures.³⁰³ To clarify the proportionality test and the suggested measures described in Art 25(1), the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) has published a “Privacy and Data Protection by Design” guide, in which it provides practical privacy by design strategies, as well as privacy techniques.³⁰⁴

Unlike privacy by design measures, privacy by default measures do not require a proportionality test (Art 25(2) GDPR) and require that “by default, only personal data which are necessary for each specific purpose of the processing are processed”.³⁰⁵ Therefore, all data processing systems (which process personal data) must have privacy-friendly default settings.³⁰⁶ The controller must configure default settings so that only personal data is processed, stored and accessed as necessary for a specific purpose.³⁰⁷ The “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” use case, for example, would need to ensure that it only collects and processes data as necessary to deliver the rehabilitation treatment, and that it does not store or use data for other purposes except as expressly authorized by the data subject.

3.2.1.6 Data Impact Assessment (Art 35 GDPR, Recitals 84, 89-93)

While privacy by design and by default measures provide proactive and preventative approaches to data protection,³⁰⁸ the requirement to undertake data protection impact assessments for “new technologies” provides a risk-based approach to protect personal data.³⁰⁹ Controllers must carry out a data protection impact assessment if the use of the new technology “is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons”.³¹⁰

Art 35(7) GDPR contains a list of minimum requirements for a data protection impact assessment. The controller must systematically describe the processing operations (taking the example of the “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” use case, the processing of health data to determine an appropriate rehabilitation regime) and the purpose of the processing (rehabilitation of patients).³¹¹ Furthermore, the controller must assess whether the processing operations are proportionate and necessary to the purpose (e.g.: is it possible to anonymize or pseudonymize the data? Is all the data necessary to achieve the purpose? How early can it be deleted?³¹²),³¹³ and the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects (e.g.: right to privacy, risk of harm for the patient’s health³¹⁴).³¹⁵ Additionally, the controller must provide a description of the planned measures and mechanisms to ensure data protection (e.g.: restriction of access permissions or use of encryption technologies³¹⁶).³¹⁷

³⁰² Art 25(1) GDPR.

³⁰³ Art 25(1) GDPR.

³⁰⁴ See Enisa, Privacy and Data Protection by Design – from policy to engineering (2014) https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/privacy-and-data-protection-by-design/at_download/fullReport (last downloaded on the 29th of April 2021).

³⁰⁵ Art 25(2) GDPR.

³⁰⁶ See *Hötzendorfer/Kastelitz/Tschohl*, in Knyrim (eds) Art 25 DSGVO para 39.

³⁰⁷ See *Hötzendorfer/Kastelitz/Tschohl*, in Knyrim (eds) Art 25 DSGVO para 39.

³⁰⁸ See *Cavoukian*, Privacy by Design: The 7 Foundational Principles (2009) <https://www.ipc.on.ca/wp-content/uploads/Resources/7foundationalprinciples.pdf> (last downloaded on the 29th of April 2021).

³⁰⁹ Art 35 GDPR. See Article 29 Data Protection Working Group, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), wp248rev.01 (2017) 4.

³¹⁰ Art 35(1) GDPR.

³¹¹ Art 35(7)(a) GDPR.

³¹² See *Trieb*, Art 35 DSGVO, Datenschutz-Folgenabschätzung in Knyrim (eds), *DatKomm* (2018) para 112.

³¹³ Art 35(7)(b) GDPR.

³¹⁴ See *Schneeberger/Stöger/Holzinger*, CD-MAKE 2020, 209 (215).

³¹⁵ Art 35(7) lit c GDPR.

³¹⁶ See *Trieb*, Art 35 DSGVO, para 116.

³¹⁷ Art 35(7)(d) GDPR.

Moreover, the controller must consult the supervisory authority before carrying out a data protection impact assessment³¹⁸ and must report on the assessment to fulfil accountability requirements.³¹⁹ While it is not obligatory to publish this report, it is often recommended in order to show good-will and trustworthiness, as well as to promote the new technology.³²⁰ Lastly, the controller must review and re-assess the assessment as necessary.³²¹

In the DT context, it is often impossible to predict the impact of data with certainty.³²² Accordingly, public administrations are likely to need to continuously review and re-assess their data protection impact assessments, particularly when using big data.

3.2.2 Product Laws

Product laws regulate the placing of products on the market, including production, import and distribution.³²³ One of the core objectives of product law is to ensure that only safe products are placed on the market.³²⁴ Products must not harm consumers (i.e.: endanger their health or lives) or the environment.³²⁵ European product law also aims to lower market barriers and facilitate trading.³²⁶ As mentioned in the introduction to this Chapter, we focus on two horizontal product laws here and the issues DTs may pose for them: the GPSD and the PLD.³²⁷

The GPSD contains general safety requirements for products³²⁸ and aims to ensure that only safe products are placed on the market.³²⁹ For this purpose, the GPSD imposes obligations on producers, and distributors.³³⁰ The member states must ensure compliance with the GPSD, authorize national authorities that may impose sanctions,³³¹ and notify the European Commission if measures are taken concerning unsafe products.³³²

The PLD regulates the liability for harm caused by a defective product.³³³ It applies to all movable products and immovable products as long as they are incorporated into another movable product.³³⁴ The current wording does not cover stand-alone software.³³⁵ The PLD creates strict liability for defective products in addition to any existing remedies under other law where the product “does not provide the safety which a person is entitled to expect”.³³⁶

These two directives face certain challenges in addressing DTs. For example, while DTs integrated into a physical product, such as the “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” use case, would be covered by the PLD, “intangible” DTs

³¹⁸ Art 36 1) GDPR.

³¹⁹ See *Trieb*, Art 35 DSGVO, para 118.

³²⁰ See Article 29 Data Protection Working Group, wp248rev.01, 18; *Trieb*, Art 35 DSGVO, para 118; *Schneeberger/Stöger/Holzinger*, CD-MAKE 2020, 209 (216).

³²¹ Art 35 11) GDPR.

³²² In regard to the prediction problem of Big Data see *Ehrke-Rabel*, Data 310.

³²³ See *Grabenwarter/Holoubek*, *Europäisches und öffentliches Wirtschaftsrecht*⁴ II (2008) 85.

³²⁴ See *Grabenwarter/Holoubek*, *Wirtschaftsrecht*⁴ 85.

³²⁵ See *Grabenwarter/Holoubek*, *Wirtschaftsrecht*⁴ 85.

³²⁶ See *Grabenwarter/Holoubek*, *Wirtschaftsrecht*⁴ 88.

³²⁷ Directive 85/374/EEC.

³²⁸ See *Ruohonen*, *Assessing the Readability of Policy Documents on the Digital Single Market of the European Union*, *Computers and Society* 2021, 5.

³²⁹ Art 1 GPSD.

³³⁰ Art 5 GPSD.

³³¹ Recital 23 GPSD.

³³² Art 12 GPSD; *Ruohonen*, *Computers and Society* 2021, 4.

³³³ See *Ruohonen*, *Computers and Society* 2021, 8.

³³⁴ Art 2 PLD.

³³⁵ See *Schneeberger/Stöger/Holzinger*, CD-MAKE 2020, 209 (220 f); *Harned/Lungren/Rajpurkar*, *Machine vision, medical AI and malpractice*, *Harvard Journal of Law and Technology Digest* 2019, 8.

³³⁶ Art 6 PLD.

which are not embedded into a physical product would not. The EU has already noted this gap,³³⁷ and address this in regards to AI systems in the proposed AI Regulation: “as a component of a product, an AI system can be physically integrated into the product (embedded) or serve the functionality of the product without being integrated therein (non-embedded).”³³⁸

Further, these EU product safety laws do not currently expressly address the specific risks of DTs or create classifications for different levels of risk.³³⁹ DTs are often functionally opaque³⁴⁰ and liability or product issues could be more difficult to resolve.³⁴¹ Their functionality is also often not available to the general public³⁴² and this may not always be possible to remedy.³⁴³ Further, both the PLD³⁴⁴ and the GPSD³⁴⁵ are focused on the time at which a product is placed on the market. For example, the PLD provides that a producer will not be liable if “the state of scientific and technical knowledge at the time when he put the product into circulation was not such as to enable the existence of the defect to be discovered”.³⁴⁶ However, DTs might experience new or latent issues as they continue to develop after deployment, such as through updates, patches or machine learning.³⁴⁷ In line with the precautionary principle, public administrations should be conscious of future as well as current risks, and the existing product safety laws may not be equipped to capture these risks.

The proposed AI Regulation demonstrates that the Commission seems aware of these issues and is likely to address them in the future. Although the proposed AI Regulation only applies to “AI systems”, this is defined broadly and would cover a range of DTs or components of DTs. The proposed AI Regulation also contains a range of transparency obligations relating to high-risk and certain types of AI systems³⁴⁸ and would create detailed reporting and risk assessment obligations beyond the time of deployment.³⁴⁹ It would also take a risk-based approach to product safety, differentiating between uses of AI that create (i) an unacceptable risk, (ii) a high risk, and (iii) low or minimal risk. Prohibited AI systems would be those that are “unacceptable as contravening Union values, for instance by violating fundamental rights”.³⁵⁰ We explore the proposed AI Regulation more in Chapter 3.3.4.

3.2.3 Equality Directives

The equality directives aim to put the principle of equal treatment (discussed in Chapter 3.1.2.3) into effect in member states,³⁵¹ with uneven levels of success. Complexities such as intersectional discrimination resulting from a combination of different grounds are not yet captured by equality laws,³⁵² but are likely to be in future.

³³⁷ See European Commission, COM (2020) 65 final, 14.

³³⁸ See European Commission, COM (2021) 206 final 14.

³³⁹ In regard to AI see European Commission, COM (2020) 65 final, 14 f.

³⁴⁰ See *Buiten/De Streel/Peitz*, EU Liability Rules for the age of Artificial Intelligence (2021) 27.

³⁴¹ In regard to AI see European Commission, COM (2020) 65 final, 14.

³⁴² *Ehrke-Rabel*, Data 311.

³⁴³ *Ehrke-Rabel*, Data 311; *Buiten/De Streel/Peitz*, Liability 27.

³⁴⁴ Art 7(b) PLD.

³⁴⁵ Art 1(1) GPSD.

³⁴⁶ Art 7(e) PLD.

³⁴⁷ In regard to AI see European Commission, COM (2020) 65 final, 14; *Schneeberger/Stöger/Holzinger*, CD-MAKE 2020, 209 (220 f); *Chatzipanagiotis*, Product Liability Directive and Software Updates of Automated Vehicles, SETN (2020) 3 f.

³⁴⁸ See European Commission, COM (2021) 206 final Arts 10, 13, 52.

³⁴⁹ For example, Art 9 requires a risk management system that “shall consist of a continuous iterative process run throughout the entire lifecycle of a high-risk AI system, requiring regular systematic updating”.

³⁵⁰ European Commission, COM (2021) 206 final Explanatory Memorandum 5.2.2.

³⁵¹ See Art 1 Council Directive 2000/78/EC.

³⁵² See C-443/15, *David L. Parris vs Trinity College Dublin* para 80.

Equal treatment directives were originally confined to addressing discrimination on the basis of sex in employment.³⁵³ A 2004 directive also covered access to goods and services,³⁵⁴ particularly targeted at prohibiting discrimination on the basis of sex in insurance premium calculations.³⁵⁵

However, the EU's wide powers under the TFEU to adopt anti-discrimination laws have led to an array of directives targeted at implementing the principle of equality into EU law.

The Race Equality Directive³⁵⁶ prohibits discrimination on the basis of race or ethnicity in healthcare, education, employment, social security and housing.³⁵⁷ It prohibits indirect discrimination, where an apparently neutral provision or practice disadvantages persons of a certain race or ethnicity, unless that provision or practice can be "objectively justified by a legitimate aim and the means of achieving that aim are appropriate and necessary".³⁵⁸ The Race Equality Directive also does not apply to discrimination on the basis of nationality or third country nationals' legal status.³⁵⁹

The Framework Employment Directive³⁶⁰ has a narrower focus in terms of areas of application, as it only applies to discrimination in the labor market.³⁶¹ However, it includes prohibited grounds of discrimination on the basis of religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation.³⁶² Similarly to the fundamental rights charters, the directive has a general caveat that it is "without prejudice to measures laid down by national law which, in a democratic society, are necessary for public security, for the maintenance of public order and the prevention of criminal offences, for the protection of health and for the protection of the rights and freedoms of others".³⁶³

An Equal Treatment Directive has been proposed, which would implement the principle of equal treatment between persons, irrespective of religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation. Rather than focusing on employment, it would extend to other aspects of life such as access to goods and services, healthcare, and education.³⁶⁴ It would also equalize protection of these prohibited grounds, rather than some characteristics (racial or ethnic origin and sex) being more protected than others under the currently inconsistent framework.³⁶⁵ However, progress on implementing this proposal has stalled as political consensus is lacking.³⁶⁶

³⁵³ See Directives 75/117/EEC (equal pay) 79/7/EEC (equality in social security), 92/85/EEC (protection of pregnancy and maternity), 2010/18/EU (parental leave), 2010/41/EU (self-employment). Most gender equality directives have now been consolidated under Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006 on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation (recast) [2006] OJ L204/23.

³⁵⁴ Council Directive 2004/113/EC of 13 December 2004 implementing the principle of equal treatment between men and women in the access to and supply of goods and services [2004] OJ L373/37.

³⁵⁵ Council Directive 2004/113/EC Art 5.

³⁵⁶ Council Directive 2000/43 [2000] OJ L180/22.

³⁵⁷ Art 3(1).

³⁵⁸ Art 2(b).

³⁵⁹ Art 3(2).

³⁶⁰ Council Directive 2000/78/EC of 27 November 2000 establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation [2000] OJ L303/16.

³⁶¹ Art 3(1).

³⁶² Art 1.

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³⁶⁴ See Council of the European Union, Progress Report: Proposal for a Council Directive on implementing the principle of equal treatment between persons irrespective of religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation 9734/18 (2018).

³⁶⁵ See European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, Fundamental Rights Report 2020

https://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra_uploads/fra-2020-fundamental-rights-report-2020_en.pdf (last downloaded on the 20th of April 2021).

³⁶⁶ See European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, Report 2020; *Craig/de Búrca*, EU law: text, cases, and materials⁶ (2015), 893.

The prohibitions on discrimination in access to goods and services and indirect discrimination can raise concerns in the context of automated decision making, where DTs may be used to calculate entitlements on the basis of prohibited grounds or proxies for those grounds (such as postcodes). Public administrations should ensure that DTs do not operate on these bases, and strive to introduce DTs that reflect the principles and laws of equality rather than risk undermining them. To future-proof DTs, public administrations should also operate from the premise that discrimination on the basis of any characteristic is not acceptable, regardless of whether that discrimination reflects a ground currently covered by existing law.

3.2.4 The Proposed AI Regulation

On 21 April 2021, the European Commission published the proposed AI Regulation.³⁶⁷ Following on from the White Paper on AI from 19 February 2020, it aims to address the risks associated with certain uses of AI “by proposing a legal framework for trustworthy AI”.³⁶⁸ Based on both Art 114 and 16 of TFEU, it is designed to complement existing EU law and be fully consistent with other legal provisions that already regulate AI.³⁶⁹ Its primary objective is to “ensure the proper functioning of the internal market by setting harmonized rules in particular on the development, placing on the Union market and the use of products and services making use of AI technologies or provided as stand-alone AI systems”.³⁷⁰

The Declaration of Cooperation on AI signified a commitment to a common approach to regulating AI from member states.³⁷¹ Avoiding a fragmented national-level framework for DTs is a common concern,³⁷² and a coordinated approach across national, supranational and supervisory bodies is perceived as necessary to ensure consistency and understanding of the implications of DTs for human rights.³⁷³ The proposed AI Regulation reflects this commitment to a “European approach” to regulating DTs.

Its definition of AI systems is broad, including software that can “generate outputs such as content, predictions, recommendations, or decisions influencing the environments they interact with”.³⁷⁴ Systems are classified into prohibited, high-risk, certain systems that carry specific transparency requirements, and low-risk. The intention is to be “as neutral as possible” in the definition of AI systems to enable future adaptation to new technologies.³⁷⁵

The proposed AI Regulation would apply to a public authority as a “provider” where it develops an AI system or has an AI system developed “with a view to placing it on the market or putting it into service under its own name or trademark, whether for payment or free of charge”,³⁷⁶ or as a “user” where it uses an AI system “under its authority”.³⁷⁷

³⁶⁷ See European Commission, Proposal for a Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council Laying Down Harmonised Rules On Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) And Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts, COM (2021) 206 final.

³⁶⁸ COM (2021) 206 final Explanatory Memorandum at 1.1.

³⁶⁹ COM (2021) 206 final Explanatory Memorandum at 1.2.

³⁷⁰ COM (2021) 206 final Explanatory Memorandum at 2.1.

³⁷¹ See European Commission, Declaration, Cooperation on Artificial Intelligence (2018).

³⁷² See European Commission, White Paper on Artificial Intelligence (2020) 2: “A common European approach to AI is necessary to reach sufficient scale and avoid the fragmentation of the single market. The introduction of national initiatives risks to endanger legal certainty, to weaken citizens’ trust and to prevent the emergence of a dynamic European industry”.

³⁷³ See European Parliament, Resolution (2016/2225(INI)).

³⁷⁴ COM (2021) 206 final Art 3.

³⁷⁵ *Ivanova*, Presentation at ETAPAS Workshop (2021).

³⁷⁶ COM (2021) 206 final Art 3.

³⁷⁷ COM (2021) 206 final Art 3.

The proposed AI Regulation would ban the placing on the market, putting into service or use of four types of prohibited AI systems:³⁷⁸ a) systems that use subliminal techniques to distort behavior in a way that is likely to cause a person physical or psychological harm; b) systems that exploit the vulnerabilities of a group of persons due to age or disability to distort behavior in a way that is likely to cause a person physical or psychological harm; c) if deployed by public authorities, systems that evaluate or classify the trustworthiness of people based on behavior or characteristics, and then use that “social score” to deliver detrimental treatment to people in social contexts unrelated to the contexts in which the data was originally generated or collected, or in a way that is unjustified or proportionate to their social behavior or its gravity; and d) systems that use “real time” remote biometric identification systems in public places for law enforcement, except as necessary for listed objectives.

High-risk AI systems would be permitted but would carry a range of obligations for providers and users. The “high-risk” classification applies to AI systems that form part of products covered by product safety legislation listed in Annex II, including the Medical Devices Directive³⁷⁹ and various directives related to dangerous substances, equipment, toys and infrastructure. Further high-risk AI systems are also specifically listed in Annex III, and would include systems intended to be used for making decisions in relation to employment,³⁸⁰ access to and enjoyment of essential private and public services, such as social assistance, credit, and emergency responses,³⁸¹ law enforcement³⁸² and administration of justice.³⁸³ This definition is particularly pertinent to the public administration, as almost all applications of AI systems in the public sector are deemed high-risk by this definition.

For these high-risk systems, particular requirements around data and data governance would apply, including selecting appropriate training, testing and validation data sets.³⁸⁴ High-risk AI systems would also need to be accompanied by information explaining their purpose and use³⁸⁵ and their operation would need to be “sufficiently transparent to enable users to interpret the system’s output and use it appropriately”.³⁸⁶ Human oversight would need to be ensured over high-risk AI systems³⁸⁷ and be accurate, robust and secure.³⁸⁸ Providers of high-risk AI systems would be obliged to comply with these requirements as well as further quality and risk management,³⁸⁹ conformity assessment³⁹⁰ and documentation³⁹¹ requirements and mandatory rights breach reporting (akin to data breach reporting required under the GDPR).³⁹²

Certain other AI systems would also carry heightened transparency obligations. In particular, those that are designed to interact with natural persons would need to inform those persons that they are interacting with an AI, unless it is obvious from the circumstances;³⁹³ those that use emotion recognition or biometric characterization to identify emotions would need to inform affected persons of “the operation of the system”,³⁹⁴ and systems that manipulate images to resemble real things (“deep fakes”) would need to state that the content has been artificially

³⁷⁸ COM (2021) 206 final Art 5.

³⁷⁹ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices [2017] OJ L 117/1.

³⁸⁰ COM (2021) 206 final Annex III s 4.

³⁸¹ COM (2021) 206 final Annex III s 5.

³⁸² COM (2021) 206 final Annex III s 6.

³⁸³ COM (2021) 206 final Annex III s 8.

³⁸⁴ COM (2021) 206 final Art 10.

³⁸⁵ COM (2021) 206 final Art 13(2) and (3).

³⁸⁶ COM (2021) 206 final Art 13(1).

³⁸⁷ COM (2021) 206 final Art 14.

³⁸⁸ COM (2021) 206 final Art 15.

³⁸⁹ COM (2021) 206 final Arts 9 and 17.

³⁹⁰ COM (2021) 206 final Arts 19 and 43.

³⁹¹ COM (2021) 206 final Arts 11, 12, 18, 20, 23 and 50.

³⁹² COM (2021) 206 final Art 62.

³⁹³ COM (2021) 206 final Art 52(1).

³⁹⁴ COM (2021) 206 final Art 52(2).

created.³⁹⁵ For example, the state’s use of the “Municipality Chatbot Kari” use case would carry heightened transparency obligations as citizens interact with an AI interface.

4. Non-binding EU Legal Framework

The non-binding EU legal framework for the implementation of DTs refers to sources issued by EU law- and policy-makers that do not create binding law in themselves, but that are likely to have implications for the future binding legal framework and the interpretation of existing law. The EU’s range of recent discussion papers,³⁹⁶ white papers,³⁹⁷ declarations³⁹⁸ and communications³⁹⁹ reflect a growing concern and need to regulate DTs. We briefly note this framework here as a likely guide to future regulation.

The impact of DTs on society is a key concern in the non-binding framework. From care robots to profiling to autonomous weapons, these technologies are often implemented before the impacts on human relationships and lives can be studied.⁴⁰⁰ In general, the concern about impact on society tends to lead to a proposed requirement that a “human-centric” approach is preserved, where human wellbeing is the central focus of technology development and functionality.⁴⁰¹ This approach is partially reflected in the proposed “prohibited” categories of AI under the proposed AI Regulation, which have the potential to manipulate people’s behaviors or positions in society, or facilitate mass surveillance.⁴⁰²

Some tools, like the Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence, propose a “fundamental rights impact assessment” to be carried out before assessing an artificially intelligent technology’s ethical implications, enshrining legal considerations into the ethical process.⁴⁰³ Other sources consider how DTs shape our definitions of concepts like privacy and personal identity, and how DTs can affect the creation of law itself as soft-law governance grows in prominence and private actors play an increasing role in regulation.⁴⁰⁴

³⁹⁵COM (2021) 206 final Art 52(3).

³⁹⁶ See European Commission, Liability for Emerging Technologies (2018); European Parliament, Cost of non-Europe in robotics and artificial intelligence (2019); European Commission, Factsheet a European Approach on Artificial Intelligence (2018); European Parliament, Disruption by technology, Impacts on Politics, Economics and Society (2020); European Commission, Artificial Intelligence, real benefits (2018).

³⁹⁷ European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies, Statement on Artificial Intelligence, Robotics and ‘Autonomous’ Systems (2018); European Commission, White Paper on Artificial Intelligence.

³⁹⁸ See European Commission, Declaration, Cooperation on Artificial Intelligence (2018).

³⁹⁹ See European Commission, Communication on Artificial Intelligence (2018) 237; European Commission, Press release on Artificial Intelligence: Commission outlines a European Approach to boost investment and set ethical guidelines (2018); Council of Europe, European Ethical Charter on the use of AI (2018).

⁴⁰⁰ See Joint Research Centre Science for Policy Report AI Watch, Artificial Intelligence in Medicine and Healthcare: applications, availability and societal impact. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union (2020).

⁴⁰¹ See European Commission, Communication on Building Trust in Human-Centric AI, COM (2019) 168 final; European Commission, White Paper on Artificial Intelligence; Council of the European Union, The Charter of Fundamental Rights in the context of Artificial Intelligence and Digital Change <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/46496/st11481-en20.pdf> (last downloaded on the 20th of April 2021).

⁴⁰² See COM (2021) 206 final Art 5.

⁴⁰³ See High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, Assessment List For Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (2020); European Commission, Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) for self-assessment <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment> (last downloaded on the 20th of April 2021).

⁴⁰⁴ European Parliament, Disruption by technology, Impacts on Politics, Economics and Society (2020).

Non-binding sources also consider the benefits that DTs can bring to society, including consideration of the role of technology in addressing the COVID-19 pandemic,⁴⁰⁵ although this discussion again tends to be focused on AI applications.⁴⁰⁶ The European Commission has also pushed for EU-wide training and innovative approaches relating to DTs,⁴⁰⁷ such as establishing Digital Innovation Hubs.⁴⁰⁸ As evidenced by the ETAPAS project, we can therefore expect to see considerable investment and promotion of DTs by the public sector alongside regulation.

5. Conclusion

The EU legal framework for the implementation of DTs in the public administrative sector is a combination of general primary law sources, including the founding EU treaties, fundamental rights, and key principles, and more specific horizontal and vertical secondary law sources that regulate particular areas of application.

Primary law lays out principles and cornerstones of the EU legal framework that act as constraints on public administration action by requiring decision-makers to act only where they are competent to do so, where market freedoms are protected, where action is proportionate and fundamental rights and equality protected. However, primary law can also empower public administrations to act, such as through the precautionary principle that enables decision-makers to act in a precautionary way when it is not yet possible to quantify a risk.

The implementation of DTs could interfere with the fundamental right to human dignity. Individuality and personal identity could be affected if DTs collect large amounts of data and treat humans merely as data objects,⁴⁰⁹ and the use of automated decision making could interfere with human dignity through its potential to magnify biases.⁴¹⁰ The right to life does not grant a right to treatment by medical DTs, such as the use of the “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” use case. The right to life, however, could oblige public administrations to implement safety standards for the use of DTs. The rights to private life and data protection contain further constraints on the use of DTs, as many involve the collection of personal data. DTs must only use data as necessary for and proportionate to a legitimate objective, ensuring appropriate safeguards are in place. The use of DTs to moderate or regulate misinformation also raises concerns regarding freedom of speech. They may be permissible where misinformation has been restricted by law. However, DTs would need to be able to differentiate between statements of fact and value judgements and would likely need human oversight.

Secondary law further concretizes primary law’s general rules. For example, human dignity plays a role in the GDPR through safeguards against ADM, such as obtaining human intervention or being able to express one’s point of view,⁴¹¹ and in the equality directives through prohibitions on equal discrimination and attempts to ensure equal access to goods and services. Product safety laws contain concrete obligations to ensure that products placed on the market are safe. The GDPR contains concrete rights (such as the right to access information and the duty to provide information) to protect the privacy and data of data subjects and provides specific rights (such as privacy by design and by default) to ensure transparency during data processing. It also incorporates the precautionary principle and the proportionality principle into law through data protection impact assessments and a proportionality test for privacy by design measures.

⁴⁰⁵ See Council of the European Union, The Charter of Fundamental Rights in the context of Artificial Intelligence and Digital Change <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/46496/st11481-en20.pdf> (last downloaded on the 20th of April 2021)..

⁴⁰⁶ See European Commission, Factsheet; European Commission, real benefits (2018); European Parliament, Should we fear Artificial Intelligence (2018).

⁴⁰⁷ See European Commission, Factsheet; EIT-Digital, Artificial Intelligence Report.

⁴⁰⁸ European Commission, Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) in Europe <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/digital-innovation-hubs-dihs-europe> (last downloaded on the 20th of April 2021).

⁴⁰⁹ See *Aizenberg/Van den Hoven*, Designing 5.

⁴¹⁰ See *Ehrke-Rabel*, Data 311 f.

⁴¹¹ Art 22(3) GDPR.

Accordingly, there are a range of existing constraints, requirements and opportunities for the public administration under the existing EU legal framework. However, the fragmented nature of the legal framework when it comes to DTs means that there are some issues that slip through regulatory gaps, such as limited and ambiguous protections from automated decision-making, product laws that do not apply to software, and discrimination laws that do not account for discrimination by proxy. Existing laws may be ill-equipped to address novel issues of opacity, complexity, bias, unpredictability, and autonomy⁴¹² arising from DTs.

These problems have partially been recognized by the EU through the non-binding legal framework and in the proposed AI Regulation, at least in relation to AI systems. While the broad definition of AI under the proposed AI Regulation is likely to capture a range of DTs, it focusses on increasing trust in AI specifically, by banning certain types of AI and categorizing others according to current concerns. This focus is reflected in its list of certain AI systems that have particular transparency requirements, which address topical concerns of human-seeming interfaces, emotion recognition and “deep fakes”.⁴¹³ The proposed AI Regulation’s focus on AI systems means that it is not likely to become the “one-stop-shop” of regulation for DTs in the public sector. However, its flexible structure can evolve to capture more technologies⁴¹⁴ and serve as a blueprint for further regulation. Most relevantly for public administrations considering the implementation of DTs, the proposed AI Regulation also gives an idea of the monitoring, quality, reporting and documentation requirements that could be expected, and is a clear signal from the Commission of its key concerns.

The risk-based approach taken under the proposed AI Regulation signals the direction of future DT regulation. Where the existing framework has concretized some obligations that will apply to most DTs, most notably through the GDPR, we expect that its current fragmentation will lead to further risk-based steps to strengthen the EU legal framework for the implementation of DTs in the public administrative sector.

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⁴¹³ COM (2021) 206 final Art 52.

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